

EDEN ISS

Hardware Interface Document

prepared for

WP 2.1 - System Requirements & Interface Analysis

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Executive summary

This document provides the system hardware interface requirements of the EDEN ISS project.

It includes the definition of all Mobile Test Facility (MTF) external and internal hardware interface requirements. A separate document, D2.2 EDEN ISS Software Interface Requirements, defines all the software interface requirements including definition of telemetry from MTF sensors and telecommands used for controlling specific MTF equipment.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	HTK	HTK Hamburg GmbH
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Test	IS	Ion-Selective
AMS	Air Management System	ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	ISS	International Space Station
AST	Airbus Defence and Space	LabVIEW	Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench
ATS	Analogue Test Site	LED	Light Emitting Diode
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
CDH	Command and Data Handling	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
CE	Concurrent Engineering	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
CEF	Concurrent Engineering Facility	PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	PoE	Power over Ethernet
DLO	Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek (Wageningen University and Research)	RD	Reference Document
DLR-RY	German Aerospace Center Institute of Space Systems	SPO	Sound Pressure Level
EC	Electrical Conductivity	SRD	Systems Requirement Document
ECC	EDEN ISS Control Center	SS	Service Section
EDEN	Evolution & Design of Environmentally-closed Nutrition-Sources	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
EDR	European Drawer Rack	TBC	To Be Clarified
E-Nose	Electronic Nose	TBD	To Be Determined
EP	Elevated Platform	TCS	Thermal Control System
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
ESC	External Storage Container	UIP	Utility Interface Panel
EU	European Union	UoG	University of Guelph
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	WP	Work Package
HS	Heliospectra BA		

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall objectives of the EDEN ISS project

Long-term human presence in space will require the development of bio-regenerative life support systems (BLSS). The integration of such systems into manned habitats decreases the resupply requirements by generating human resources via biological processes. The EDEN ISS project aims to validate selected subsystems and key technologies up to a TRL of 6 according to the standards described in the Technology Readiness Levels Handbook for Space Applications of the European Space Agency (ESA) [RD1]. Therefore the project will demonstrate operational capability of key technologies in an environment with some characteristics relevant to space. For this purpose a dedicated test campaign will be executed at the Neumayer Station III in Antarctica where a deployed mobile test facility will be operated by an isolated overwintering crew. This deployment will also be preparatory research for a future plant production system at the ISS.

The main objectives of EDEN ISS are shown in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Objectives of the EDEN ISS project

Objective 1	Manufacturing a space analogue mobile test facility to provide representative mass flows and proper test environments for plant cultivation technologies as an essential on-ground preparatory activity for future space exploration.
Objective 2	Integration and test of key elements for plant cultivation in 1) an ISPR-like system (International Standard Payload Rack) for future test on-board ISS and 2) a Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) to prepare for closed-loop bio-regenerative life support systems.
Objective 3	Adaption, integration, fine-tuning and demonstration of key technologies and their functionality in respective laboratory environments and (under highly isolated conditions) in an Antarctic environment.
Objective 4	Development and demonstration of operation techniques and processes for higher plant cultivation to achieve reliable and safe production of high-quality food.
Objective 5	Study of microbial behavior and countermeasures in plant-based closed ecosystems and their impacts on isolated crews.
Objective 6	Actively advancing knowledge related to human spaceflight and transformation of research results into terrestrial applications , by actively leveraging synergies between space and non-space consortium partners.

1.2 Summary state-of-the-art: Bio-regenerative life support systems and architecture

The unique aspect of EDEN ISS is the focus on the key technologies and procedures associated with higher plant cultivation and high quality safe food production. This means that instead of dealing with all the different aspects of a BLSS, the envisioned project focuses on an essential target area. Targeting only this area guarantees a higher scientific outcome than spreading the research focus too broadly. Therefore, the EDEN ISS consortium will advance the current state-of-the-art through several means:

- Develop a **high fidelity ISPR cultivation system with approximately 1 m² production area**, thereby enhancing the feasibility of Europe providing the ISS with a plant production facility capable of almost an order of magnitude increase to current orbit production areas.
- Deploy a European constructed, **highly integrated, mobile greenhouse module test facility to Antarctica**. After completion of the project, the test facility will be used for further on-going BLSS investigations and will be open for experiments to the European BLSS community.
- Increase the TRL of a **microgravity NDS** built with materials capable of reducing possible biological contamination and including **advanced on-line ion-selective sensors**.
- Advance the TRL of **spectrally tunable LED lighting systems** for highly reliable and remotely operated plant production systems. Energy conservation will be improved through the development and use of **advanced LED heat capture techniques and intra-canopy lighting**. Experimentally determine

optimal light recipes for 5-10 crops and employ these recipes to maximize production within the mobile test facility.

- Increase of the TRL of relevant technologies in the field of **bio-detection and decontamination** of BLSS.
- Further develop proper **plant handling and food safety procedures** for higher plant cultivation in closed systems comparable to ISS and future long-duration space missions.

Table 1-2 provides a summary of the specific advances to the current state-of-the-art for the primary focus areas of the EDEN ISS project.

Table 1-2: Overview and comparison between state-of-the-art and beyond state-of-the-art

System	State-of-the-art	Beyond state-of-the-art
Greenhouse module test facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple ‘Salad Machines’, small food quantities • Cultivation processes and plant health monitoring is rather hands-on with limited automation • Bulk of Antarctic systems have been expeditioner/hobby- based and constructed with materials found on-site • Limited to no remote commanding • Single surface production systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce higher quantities of fresh crops in order to achieve higher mission fidelity • Highly integrated test module, considering all necessary subsystems and analyzing the overall mass production principles • Detailed quantification of pre- and post-processing analysis, cleaning and general crew time allocations • Enhance reliability of remote greenhouses through telepresence (tools and competency)
ISS plant production facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small-scale production areas (~0.1 m²) • Science driven • Negligible food production • Low to marginal environmental control reliability (some exceptions) • Non-scalable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium-scale production areas (~1 m²) • Food production and psychological benefit driven • Non-negligible food production for repeatable safety evaluation • Well characterized and reliable environmental control • Scalable
Nutrient delivery system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil-based and soilless cultivation • On-line nutrient solution status measurements are indiscriminate (e.g. electrical conductivity) • Off-line measurements of ion-selective values are time intensive (e.g. days/ weeks) • Difficult and insufficient bio-contamination prevention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soilless cultivation is imperative • Higher yield, low water and nutrient use systems • Real-time online measurements of selective ion concentrations (e.g. new optrodes) • View of root system enhances ability of remote telemetric monitoring (e.g. aeroponic) • Nanostructured coatings for bio-contamination prevention onto surfaces
Light system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct natural light (Sun) not feasible for space greenhouses (e.g. radiation, temporal variability, system complexity) • Fluorescent, high pressure sodium, metal halide, Sulphur plasma lamp, induction lamp • PAR-specific multispectral LED light most promising candidate, but in early development stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High performance LEDs (combining a variety of monochromatic lights, specifically tailored to plant photosynthetic requirements) • Highly integrated panels and optimized with respect to mass, thermal load (active cooled), volume, and power demand • Intra-canopy lighting systems
Bio-detection and decontamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bio-detection performed by classical sampling method, wiping followed by incubation in a sample medium • Work intensive spray and wipe decontamination procedures, physico-chemical treatment or steam disinfection of small items • No possibility to disinfect hard-to-reach areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time detection of quality and quantity of microbial loads (using gas-analyzing instrument E-Nose) • High reachability (e.g. cavities, tubes and harnesses) with TransMADDS • Specific decontaminant depending on the microbial load, preventive effect, no damage of equipment
Food quality and safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory evaluation of food products for characterization of texture, flavor and palatability • Nutrient determination via solvent extraction and analysis via laboratory scale atomic absorption spectroscopy, liquid chromatography and UV-Visible spectroscopy • Lab based PCR or standard plate count techniques and microscopy employed for identification of microbial and infectious agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish sensor panel response versus physio-metric data analysis to produce a sensory evaluation protocol for use on board ISS • Rapid, non-destructive indicators of food quality • Rapid screen for microbial contamination • Food safety quick tests; new palatability analysis tools • Increase shelf lifetime for produced crops

2 Terms, definitions, conventions

2.1 Definitions and terms

Figure 2-1: Overview of EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility (MTF) main elements.

EDEN ISS Elements

Mobile Test Facility (MTF)

The EDEN ISS mobile test facility to be operated in the Antarctic at the Neumayer Station III for testing a food production system under mission relevant conditions at ISS and future planetary outposts. The MTF comprises 2 x 20 ft high-cube shipping containers joined together at their front ends. The MTF is oriented in East-West direction. (see Figure 2-1).

Service Section Container

The Service Section Container houses the main entrance at its West front end, which leads into the cold porch (or air lock) and from there on into the Service Section. The East front end of the Service Section Container is connected to the West front end of the FEG Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section Container also contains a raised floor on which the normal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.

Cold Porch

An enclosed section in the Service Section Container of the MTF that provides a climatic interface buffer between the external environment and the MTF Service

	<p><i>Section (see Figure 2-1). Used for changing clothing (weather gear to lab clothing), general storage and housing the waste liquid and fresh water tank in the sub-floor.</i></p>
Service Section (SS)	<p><i>The Service Section is housed in the Service Section Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section houses the ISPR cultivation system. Furthermore, the Service Section contains all utilities for the MTF such as power distribution, Air Management System, Thermal Control System, Nutrient Delivery System, and consoles/computers for controlling MTF, FEG and ISPR. The SS also provides a work environment for visiting personnel including desk/chair/locker and sink.</i></p>
International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR) Cultivation System	<p><i>The EDEN ISS ISPR is a ground version of the standard payload racks used on ISS. It provides all resources such as power, environmental and thermal control, nutrient delivery and data management to support 2 plant cultivation chambers for simultaneous cultivation of different plants under different environmental conditions.</i></p>
FEG Container	<p><i>The FEG Container houses the Future Exploration Greenhouse. The West front end of the FEG Container is connected to the East front end of the Service Section Container. The East front end of the FEG Container houses an emergency exit. The FEG Container also contains a raised floor on which the normal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.</i></p>
Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)	<p><i>The FEG is installed within the FEG Container. It contains rack structures mounted along the sides of the container (4 each side). Each rack can be configured with up to 4 shelves for accommodating Plant Grow Units, LED lighting, LED water cooling, nutrient delivery hardware, sensors and cameras. Also contains space in a rack for seed germination. The FEG is separated from the SS by a sealed wall. A door is provided for access from the SS. An Emergency Exit door is available at the far end of the FEG.</i></p>
<u>MTF Internal – General</u>	
Raised Floor	<p><i>Both containers of the MTF have a raised floor which is around 30 cm above the original container floor. The raised floor is held by a stainless steel structure and is the normal walking and working surface, therefore the stainless steel framework is covered with floor panels. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.</i></p>
Sub-Floor	<p><i>Space between container floor and raised floor. The free height of the subfloor is around 25 cm throughout the whole MTF. The sub-floor contains the fresh and waste water tanks inside the Cold Porch and air tubes and liquid pipes within the Service Section and the FEG. The sub-</i></p>

	<i>floor also contains a drainage basin in the Service Section and the FEG.</i>
Floor Panels	<i>The floor panels cover the raised floor and functions as the normal walking and working surface.</i>
Drainage Basin (= "sump")	<i>The drainage basin is located in the sub-floor of the Service Section and the FEG. Its purpose is to collect spilled or leaked fluids. Collected liquids are drained via pump to waste liquid tank housed in cold porch sub-floor.</i>
Wall and Ceiling Cladding	<i>Interior wall panelling that protects the MTF insulation from humidity and spilled liquids.</i>
Container-to-Container Interface	<i>Insulated space between containers for mating joints, utility piping, electric/sensor harness connectors etc.</i>

MTF Internal – Cold Porch

Main Entrance Door	<i>Main door for access to MTF. Weather sealed door with small window.</i>
Cold Porch Heaters	<i>Heater(s) in the cold porch that automatically are ON when airlock ambient temperature falls below 5°C.</i>
Cold Porch locker	<i>Container for clothing, personnel items etc. (external weather gear, lab clothing etc.).</i>
Waste Liquid Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for temporary storage of all liquid waste from the MTF.</i>
Fresh Water Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for storage of fresh water for the MTF.</i>

MTF Internal – Service Section

Service Section Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting the cold porch with the Service Section.</i>
Service Section General Lighting	<i>Overhead white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>
Service Section Window	<i>Rectangular window on the North side of the Service Section above desk facing the NM-III.</i>
Atmosphere Management System (AMS)	<i>The AMS is an automated system that actively controls a pre-determined air flow speed, temperature and composition to the FEG via air ducts and dedicated louvers. FEG atmospheric parameters monitored by the AMS are CO₂, temperature and relative humidity. Exhaust air is cycled back to the AMS from the FEG via air ducts. The AMS then controls the humidity, and temperature of the returned airflow and sterilizes using UV and filters with a combination of a pre-filter, HEPA and charcoal filter (e.g., for ethylene) prior to cycling back to the FEG (which, to the extent possible, has a closed atmospheric environment). The AMS also has a separate Service Section air control system ('fresh air system'), which uses external air drawn into the Cold Porch and subsequently passed to the Service Section as a source of fresh air (controlled for temperature and humidity).</i>

Argus	<p><i>The Argus System is an all-in-one hardware and software platform for instrumentation monitoring, data acquisition, data logging, alarms, and automated equipment control. EDEN ISS uses Argus for monitoring and control of the Nutrient Delivery System, Atmosphere Management System, Thermal Control System and overall MTF system.</i></p>
Nutrient Delivery System (NDS)	<p><i>An automatic system for supplying nutrient feed to the Plant Cultivation Units in the FEG. The NDS comprises 2 individual bulk nutrient solutions that can be automatically modified with respect to acid, base and nutrient salt concentration prior to being pumped to the FEG Plant Cultivation Units. The NDS monitors and controls the nutrient composition for electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, ion-selective concentrations (specific ions), temperature and ozone concentration (measurement in air - for safety purposes). The bulk nutrient solutions are stored in two 250 L tanks. Fresh water is supplied to the nutrient mixing system from an approximate 300 L tank. Waste liquids are pumped to the waste tank in the subfloor of the Cold Porch. The NDS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.</i></p>
Nutrient Tank(s)	<p><i>Two 250 L tanks each containing a specific bulk nutrient solution for the Nutrient Delivery System (NDS).</i></p>
Power Distribution System	<p><i>The Power Distribution System (PDS) distributes a stabilized 230 VAC power supply to all of the MTF elements requiring electrical power. The PDS also provides 24 VDC and 12 VDC power to selective systems such as the ISPR. The PDS is connected to the Neumayer Station III overall electrical power supply of 230 VAC by land cable.</i></p>
Thermal Control System (TCS)	<p><i>The Thermal Control System (TCS) provides individual water-cooling for the Atmosphere Management System (AMS), the ISPR and the LED panels in the FEG Plant Grow Units. The TCS provides water to each of these cooling loops at a pre-defined temperature. The return flow temperature is monitored by the TCS and the system automatically adjusts a set of three-way valves to ensure sufficient cooling. Waste heat is removed via heat exchangers in each TCS loop and cycled outside of the MTF via separate fluid loops (water + Tyfocor) to a passive external radiator mounted on the top of the MTF. The TCS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.</i></p>
Uninterruptible Power Supply	<p><i>The Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) provides emergency power to specific systems in case of main power failure from the Neumayer Station III. Presently designed to provide 1400 W for 36 – 115 minutes (depending on number of modules) at 70% load.</i></p>

MTF Internal – ISPR

ISPR Cold Plate	<i>A water cooled plate for mounting items that need removal of excess heat during operation.</i>
ISPR Drawer	<i>A dedicated removable drawer in the ISPR for housing payloads. Each drawer is provided with standard interface resources such as power, thermal cooling, data handling etc. The number of available drawers is dependent upon the design function of the ISPR</i>
ISPR Fire Alarm LED	<i>Red LED smoke/fire light on front of ISPR that is activated by interior smoke sensor in case of fire.</i>
LabVIEW	<i>LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench) is a system-design platform and development environment for a visual programming language from National Instruments. The EDEN ISS ISPR uses this application for monitoring and control of all the ISPR sensor parameters.</i>
Plant Cultivation Chamber	<i>A dedicated plant grow unit housed in a drawer of the ISPR. There are 2x chambers in the ISPR, one for short plants and one for tall plants. Each chamber contains a root zone, a plant growth zone and a LED illumination panel. Each chamber has provision for nutrient feed to the root zone, CO₂ and fresh air to the plant zone as well as water cooling and electrical power for the LEDs. The chambers are monitored by sensors via the ISPR LabVIEW computer application software for CO₂ and relative humidity in the plant growth zone as well as soil temperature, moisture, and electrical conductivity in the root zone. Two video cameras are provided in each chamber to monitor overall plant health.</i>
Rack Maintenance Switch	<i>A 2-position manually operated switch that when set in open position cuts all power to ISPR. Used to assure safety of personnel when accessing inside of ISPR for maintenance purposes etc.</i>
Utility Interface Panel (UIP)	<i>Interface panel at base of ISPR for connecting external utilities such as water, power, data etc. via ISPR standard connectors.</i>

Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)

FEG Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting Service Section with the Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG).</i>
Emergency Exit	<i>Weather sealed door that connects FEG to exterior platform. During normal operations only to be used during fire or chemical emergency if path to main door in airlock is not accessible (may be used for basic facility access during the construction and test phases).</i>
FEG General Lighting	<i>Overhead dimmable white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>

Aeroponics	<i>Aeroponics is the process of growing plants in an air or mist environment without the use of soil or an aggregate medium.</i>
Hydroponics	<i>Hydroponics is a subset of hydroculture and is a method of growing plants using mineral nutrient solutions, in water, without soil. Terrestrial plants may be grown with their roots in the mineral nutrient solution only, or in an inert medium, such as perlite or gravel.</i>
LED Panel	<i>A single LED lamp with variable light output from 150 - 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ and individual wavelength setting all controlled by Ethernet commanding/monitoring via Argus computer in Service Section. The lamps are water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System. One LED panel is utilized per single Plant Growth Unit (except in the instance of intracanopy lighting).</i>
Photosynthetically Active Radiation	<i>The Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) designates the spectral range (wave band) of solar radiation from 400 to 700 nanometers that photosynthetic organisms are able to use in the process of photosynthesis.</i>
Louver	<i>An opening in the incoming FEG air ducts that can be manually controlled to manipulate the airflow in the plants. Each horizontal FEG air duct includes 8 louvers.</i>

Figure 2-2: Overview of Plant Grow Unit components and topology of FEG Plant Grow Racks.

Plant Grow Chamber	<i>An alternative terminology for the interior of the FEG.</i>
Plant Grow Rack	<i>A standard rack structure in the FEG comprising shelves for accommodating the Plant Grow Units. There are in</i>

	<i>total eight Plant Grow Racks in the FEG, four on the left (North) side and four on the right (South) side. Each rack is individually numbered as follows:</i>
	<i>When facing Emergency Exit from FEG door, the racks on the left (North) side are numbered L1, L2, L3 and L4, those on the right (South) side R1, R2, R3 and R4. Each rack can be individually configured with up to 8 Plant Grow Units (see Figure 2-2).</i>
<i>Plant Growth Level</i>	<i>The level in the Plant Grow Unit that separates the plant root volume in the Plant Grow Trays from the plant foliage section (see Figure 2-2).</i>
<i>Plant Grow Unit</i>	<i>A standard plant growth dedicated volume available in various heights (52 cm, 104 cm and 208 cm) dependent on plant size. The unit comprises from top to bottom; an LED panel with water cooling, a plant leaf section, a Plant Grow Tray with holes for shoots and a root zone with an aeroponics nutrient delivery system.</i> <i>Each Unit is numbered either 1, 2, 3 or 4 from bottom to top depending on configuration. For example the first rack on the left side has 4 Plant Grow Units and is therefore numbered L1-1, L1-2, L1-3 and L1-4 from bottom to top.</i>
<i>Plant Grow Tray</i>	<i>A standard plant growing tray, 40 cm by 60 cm, comprises an enclosed lower Root Zone section for housing the plant root system and nutrient delivery diffusers. The upper surface of the Root Zone section has various hole sizes/number depending on plant height/ species and is termed the Shoot Zone (see Figure 2-2).</i>
<i>Seed Germination Unit</i>	<i>A dedicated unit for germinating seeds prior to transfer of shoots to Plant Grow Units. Will be housed in the left-hand side end rack, position L4 (see Figure 2-2).</i>
<u>MTF External</u>	
<i>Platform External Walkway</i>	<i>Walkway on platform around the perimeter of the MTF.</i>
<i>Safety Railing</i>	<i>Railing for safety purposes on sides of MTF access stairs, platform walkway perimeter, and a portion of the MTF roof.</i>
<i>MTF Access Stairs</i>	<i>Stairway with safety rails allowing personnel access from ground to elevated platform level and the MTF entrance hatch.</i>
<i>Door Lighting</i>	<i>Lighting mounted over the top of the main entrance and the emergency exit doors to illuminate the space in front of the respective door.</i>
<i>Platform External Lighting</i>	<i>Fixed lighting around perimeter of MTF.</i>

MTF Roof Access Ladder	<i>Vertical ladder for access to roof of MTF mounted (but likely to be transportable) on the West side of the West-container to the right of the main entrance.</i>
Free Cooler	<i>Roof-mounted system using fans to reject excess heat from internal MTF thermal control system into the external environment. Heat load from MTF transported to free cooler via fluid line. Fluid qualified down to -50 degC.</i>
WLAN Antenna	<i>Wireless LAN antenna for data communications between MTF and NM-III housed externally on MTF container roof.</i>
External Utility Connector(s) (EUC)	<i>The EUC(s) provide for MTF external connector for power MAIN power, 1x cable, and wireless LAN antenna for data communications and back-up signal path fire alarm warning between MTF and NM-III.</i>

Neumayer Station III (NM-III)

NM-III	<i>Neumayer Station III - permanently manned German Antarctic research facility</i>
External Storage Container (ESC)	<i>Cold storage container(s) for spares, utilities etc. 7 - 8 km from NM-III. The ESC has no environmental control system and hence stored items need to be compliant with extreme Antarctic ambient climate parameters.</i>
NM-III EDEN ISS Control Console(s)	<i>EDEN ISS monitoring/commanding console(s) in the NM-III.</i>
Multipurpose Laboratory	<i>Facility in NM-III to perform food sample processing, plant sample drying and housing EDEN ISS freezer, analysis equipment, chemical reagents etc. The multipurpose laboratory provides a floor space of ca. 25 m² and the left side of the lab (upon entry) will be devoted to EDEN ISS activities. Space in the laboratory may be somewhat restrictive during summer field seasons but upon departure of the austral summer field team, a greater space within the laboratory will be available.</i>
Freezer Storage Facility	<i>Either EDEN ISS dedicated plant sample freezer or NM-III general freezer.</i>
Chemical Storage Facility	<i>NM-III facility for safe storage of EDEN ISS chemicals such as nutrient salts, acids, bases and disinfection chemicals.</i>
Skidoos	<i>Motorized manned sledge for access to external storage container up to 10 km from NM-III</i>
Transport Sledge	<i>EDEN ISS dedicated manual sledge for transporting supplies, waste, etc. between NM-III and MTF.</i>
Polarstern Crane	<i>Crane on the research vessel Polarstern for off-loading up to 25000 kg</i>
NM-III Crane	<i>Mobile crane at Neumayer Station III to be used for constructing Elevated Platform and MTF. Maximum load 10000 kg</i>

Elevated Platform (EP)

The EP is a platform raised 2.5 m above ground level for mounting the MTF containers. The platform is reached from ground level by an inclined stairway. The platform is raised to reduce snow accumulation around the MTF.

Other Terms

DLR Control Center

Main control center for EDEN ISS at the DLR, Bremen, Germany, for monitoring MTF science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.

User Home Base

Remote EDEN ISS user facility for monitoring science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.

E-Nose

*An electronic sensor for detecting chemical off-gassing signature of pathogens such as *E. coli* and *Salmonella Spp.* Used in EDEN ISS project to monitor plant health status prior to human consumption.*

TransMADDS

An aerosol based decontamination and disinfection system for sterilizing enclosed volumes of potential pathogens harmful to both plant and human health. Use in EDEN ISS dependent on concentration of pathogens detected by E-Nose and/or swabs/culture growths.

2.2 Conventions

2.2.1 Units

The International System of Units (SI units) will be used throughout the EDEN ISS study.

For more information, refer to: <http://www.bipm.org/en/si/>.

Table 2-1: Common SI Units used in this document.

Quantity	Name	Symbol	Variations
Length	meter	m	km, mm, μm
Mass	kilogram	kg	g
Time	second	s	hr, min, sec, day, sol
Force	Newton	N	mN
Power	Watt	W	mW, kW
Temperature	Celsius	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	None
Pressure	Pascal	Pa	kPa
Illumination	lux	lx	None
Volume	litre	l or L	mL
Magnetic field	Gauss	Ga	100 MeV
Plant biologically active radiation	Total photon flux density	TPFD	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ from 280 – 800 nm

3 Antarctic environment as analogue test site

3.1 Description of Antarctic environment

Typical weather conditions at Neumayer III are provided in Figure 3-1. The presented air temperature and wind speed data were collected using the Air Chemistry Observatory situated in proximity to Neumayer Station III and suggest the mobile test facility will experience minimum temperatures of approximately -50°C in the dark season, and summer temperatures reaching just over 0°C . Due to the approximate two months of darkness (and low sun angles) at Neumayer Station III (end of May to end of July), any plant production facility operating year round must incorporate electrical lighting. Snow accumulation and drifting is another factor that must be addressed by any external Antarctic plant production facility.

Figure 3-1: Neumayer III recorded air temperature and wind speed. Air temperature (A) is provided on an hourly average from Jan 1, 2010 to Dec 31, 2012, whereas wind speed (B) on a one minute logging rate is plotted from Jan 1, 2012 to Dec 31, 2012.

3.2 Neumayer Station III as a space analogue site for testing EDEN ISS mobile test facility

Justification for Antarctic in-situ plant production at stations operated year-round is anchored in the provision of improved crew nutrition and dietary variation. A compelling and tangible benefit beyond dietary considerations is the use of plant production units as horticultural therapy tools that can help alleviate some of the psychological stressors commonly experienced during isolation. The following outlines the advantages of the Neumayer Station III as a test site for the deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility. Focus will be given to the maturation of the EDEN ISS technological and operational readiness for use on future space exploration missions.

Crew Size: The Neumayer Station III crew size varies with the season. During the summer season a team of approximately 40 to 50 people is maintained at the facility. During the Antarctic winter, a small team of normally nine crew members remains to maintain systems and continue annual science data collection. The size and duration of the overwintering team aligns well with current ISS crew sizes as well as those proposed in Moon/Mars design reference missions.

Crew Dynamics: Typical resupply schedules for an Antarctic station are very similar to current space station resupply schedules. There is a typical 9 month lag between resupply missions to Neumayer Station III, which exposes the crew to strong isolation pressure and the associated psychological responses. Unlike laboratory-based long-duration isolation studies, Antarctic crew members must count on technology to survive as there is no door that can be opened to 'end the simulation' in an emergency. Furthermore, although crew members are provided traditional recreational opportunities, growing plants is an activity where the output of a few interested crew members can be enjoyed by the entire crew. From this perspective, effects on the psychological well-being of the crew can be compared with real long-

duration space exploration scenarios, where some members of the crew can enjoy passive psychological benefits provided by the efforts of their crew mates.

Inhospitable Environment and Antarctic Treaty Requirements: The harsh environmental conditions typical of Antarctic research stations can only be found at a select few places on Earth. High winds, heavy snow fall (site dependent), low temperatures and seasonal dark periods lasting several months make this an environment where successful plant production requires advanced controlled environment technologies. The Antarctic continent is not only an extremely cold and arid desert, it is also one of the most protected, and biologically sparse environments on Earth. The Neumayer Station III greenhouse module is a high fidelity testing environment for microbiological experiments aimed at refining planetary protection protocols for long-duration human habitation of extra-terrestrial planetary bodies (e.g. Mars). The Antarctic Treaty and its associated Protocol on Environmental Protection place particular requirements on plant production facilities that provide noteworthy analogy to those required in future space-based systems.

Additionally, the initial deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility at the Neumayer Station III serves as a first step towards greater and greater incorporation of bioregenerative life support systems into Antarctic stations. This provides an opportunity to validate complex integrated systems (e.g. air, water and food interfaces) under conditions relevant to the long-term goal of operating plant production facilities on the ISS and on the surface of the Moon and Mars.

3.3 Polarstern and Neumayer Station III Transport and Crane Limits

The maximum Polarstern crane, transport, Neumayer Station III crane(s) and the elevated platform mass limits are provided in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2: Polarstern crane, Neumayer Station III crane, transport and elevated platform mass limits.

4 MTF external hardware interface requirements

4.1 Neumayer Station III

4.1.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

None. The MTF has no direct mechanical or structural interface to the NM-III because it is sited about 400 m away from the station.

4.1.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

4.1.2.1 Main power supply

4.1.2.1.1 Power Supply from NM-III

The NM-III shall provide 3-phase 230 VAC power to the MTF main power box via a > 400 m land cable initially buried approximately 50 cm under the local ice surface.

4.1.2.1.2 Main power cable physical characteristics

The main power cable from the NM-III (Faber Kabel: H07RN-F 05G70) shall have the physical characteristics as shown in Figure 4-1.

The rubber insulated cable shall have five cores, including a green-yellow ground core. The cable shall have a 47 mm outer diameter with each of its five conductors having a 70 mm² cross section.

Figure 4-1: Main power cable from NM-III physical characteristics

4.1.2.1.3 Main power electrical characteristics

The main power supply from the NM-III shall provide the MTF with electrical characteristics as shown in Table 4-1.

Parameter	Value
Rated Voltage	400 / 230 V
Rated Frequency	50 Hz
Rated Current / max Fuse	80 A
Power	55 kW

Table 4-1: Electrical characteristics of NM-III power supply

4.1.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

N/A.

4.1.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

N/A.

4.1.5 Command & Data Handling Interface Requirements

4.1.5.1 Main data link

4.1.5.1.1 Fiber optics cable from NM-III

The NM-III shall provide a fiber optics cable bundle to a 24 port switch in the MTF via a >400 m land cable initially buried approximately 50 cm under the local ice surface.

4.1.5.1.2 Fiber optics cable physical characteristics

The fiber optics cable from the NM-III shall have the physical characteristics as shown in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2: Fiber optics cable from NM-III physical characteristics

4.1.5.1.3 Fiber optics cable performance characteristics

Parameter	Value
Max. attenuation	0.5 dB/km
Nominal zero dispersion slope	0.092 ps/(nm ² -km)

Table 4-2: Performance characteristics of NM-III fiber optics cable

4.1.5.2 Backup data link

4.1.5.2.1 The NM-III shall provide a backup data link to the MTF

The NM-III shall provide a backup data link to the MTF via WLAN patch antenna.

4.1.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

None.

Note. Water, nutrients and other items and consumables will be transferred between the station and the MTF manually by the crew, using a transport sled. End of note.

4.2 Elevated Platform (EP)

4.2.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

4.2.1.1 Loads Requirements

4.2.1.1.1 Static Loads

4.2.1.1.1.1 The EP shall be designed such that it can sustain a maximum load of 48000 kg

4.2.1.1.2 Dynamic Loads

4.2.1.1.2.1 The Elevated Platform shall be capable of sustaining continuous horizontal loads in all directions caused by winds at speeds up to 50 m/s.

4.2.1.2 Height adjustment

4.2.1.2.1 The Elevated Platform shall be designed such that it can be raised periodically, to prevent snow accumulation from enveloping the MTF.

4.2.1.3 Mounting Points

4.2.1.3.1 The mounting points of the MTF containers on the EP shall be via eight twist locks welded to the load-carrying profiles of the EP (Figure 4-3).

Figure 4-3: EP fixtures (orange) for securing the MTF containers

4.2.1.3.2 The MTF containers shall have standard ISO 1161 corner fittings. The bottom corner fittings are positioned on top of L12 twist locks (90x150x190 mm), which are welded in-situ to the main EP load-bearing profiles (Figure 4-4 and [RD7]).

Figure 4-4: (Left) CAD image of a container corner fitting. (Right) Example of a manual twist lock

4.2.1.4 Power Connector and fiber optics cable Interface

4.2.1.4.1 The main power feeder from the NM-III shall be mounted on the EP and MTF as shown in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-5: Overview of MTF power feeder mounted on the EPF

4.2.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

None.

4.2.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

None.

4.2.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

None.

4.2.5 Command and Data Handling Interface Requirements

None.

4.2.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

None.

4.3 MTF External Environment and Equipment Interfaces

4.3.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

4.3.1.1 Container to Container Joint

4.3.1.1.1 *The Service Section and the FEG shall be structurally joined together via 6 bolts, 3 on both the left and right side of the containers (Figure 4-6).*

4.3.1.1.2 *The gap between the containers shall be closed with a rubber seal, which is covered by metal sheets on the outside. On the inside, the seal shall be covered by insulation material, which in turn shall be covered by high pressure laminate plates (Trespa Toplab Vertical). Floor panels shall be used to (partially) cover the gap between the two container floor structures.*

Figure 4-6: Overview of Joint Assembly between SS and FEG

Top left image: Steel bolt connecting the two containers

Top right image: Installation of the rubber seal on the FEG container

Bottom left image: Cover plate installed over the MTF containers joint

Bottom right image: Trespa plate installed over the MTF containers joint

4.3.1.1.3 The SS to FEG container joint shall be made of the following materials:

- A rubber seal
- Steel cover plates
- Polyurethane insulation
- Steel bolts
- 'Trespa' high pressure laminate plates

4.3.1.2 MTF Entrance Door

4.3.1.2.1 The MTF shall have a weather-sealed entrance door with access to the Cold Porch as shown in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-7: MTF Cold Porch entrance door

4.3.1.2.2 The MTF entrance door shall open outwards and have inner dimensions as follows:

- Width 108 cm
- Height 195 cm
- Thickness 12 cm

4.3.1.2.3 *The MTF entrance door shall be made of Cr-Ni-steel.*

4.3.1.2.4 *The MTF entrance door shall have a window, with dimensions of 40 x 60 cm, and double-layered glass.*

4.3.1.3 *Service Section Window*

4.3.1.3.1 *The Service Section shall have a glass window as shown in Figure 4-8.*

Figure 4-8: Service Section Window on north facing (direction NM-III) side-wall of container

4.3.1.3.2 *The Service Section window shall have the following dimensions:*

- Width 170 cm
- Height 80 cm
- Thickness 15 cm (window frame)

4.3.1.3.3 *The Service Section Window shall be comprised of double-layered glass.*

4.3.1.4 MTF cut-outs

4.3.1.4.1 The MTF Service Section container shall have cut-outs, as seen in Figure 4-9, to allow power and data cables as well as fluidic lines to enter and exit the container.

Figure 4-9: (Top) North side of the Service Section container. (Bottom) South side of the Service Section container

- 4.3.1.4.2 The main power cable cut-out, see Figure 4-9, shall allow the main power cable and the fiber optics cable from the NM-III station to enter the MTF.
- 4.3.1.4.3 The external power and data cable cut-out, see Figure 4-9, shall allow power and data cables to exit the MTF to connect to externally mounted equipment.
- 4.3.1.4.4 The thermal fluid lines cut-out, see Figure 4-9, shall allow fluidic lines to run between externally mounted components and internally mounted components.
- 4.3.1.4.5 The cut-outs in the MTF side walls shall be sealed using the GK-Packsystem as shown in Figure 4-10.

Figure 4-10: GK-Pack system used to seal off the MTF side wall thermal system fluid lines cut-out

- 4.3.1.4.6 The external power and data cable cut-out and the thermal fluid lines cut-out shall be protected by metal covers, see Figure 4-11.

Figure 4-11: Service Section cut-out covers

4.3.1.5 MTF FEG Emergency Exit Door

- 4.3.1.5.1 The MTF shall have an Emergency Exit door in the FEG as shown in Figure 4-12.

Figure 4-12: MTF FEG Emergency Exit door

4.3.1.5.2 *The MTF Emergency Exit door shall open outwards and have inner dimensions as follows:*

- Width 108 cm
- Height 195 cm
- Thickness 12 cm

4.3.1.5.3 *The MTF Emergency Exit door shall be made of Cr-Ni-steel.*

4.3.1.5.4 *The MTF Emergency Exit door shall have a window, with dimensions of 40 x 60 cm, with at least, double layered glass.*

4.3.1.6 *Crew access and safety equipment*

4.3.1.6.1 *The MTF shall have a ladder mounted next to the main entrance door to allow access to the roof.*

4.3.1.6.2 *The MTF shall have a safety cage mounted over the ladder to provide adequate safety to crew climbing the ladder.*

4.3.1.6.3 *The MTF shall have a horizontal safety system on the roof of both containers to prevent crew from falling off when working on the roof of the MTF.*

4.3.1.7 Air Management System

4.3.1.7.1 The MTF shall have an external inlet on the side of the Service Section for the provision of fresh (ambient) air into the Service Section of the MTF as shown in Figure 4-13.

Figure 4-13: Overview of the MTF external air ducts for the AMS inlet

4.3.1.7.2 The MTF shall have a mounting system to allow for the fixation of CO₂ bottles, as shown in Figure 4-14.

4.3.1.7.3 The MTF shall have mounting holes to allow for installation of ITEM profiles, which are used to mount CO₂ gas regulator panels, as shown in Figure 4-14.

Figure 4-14: Mechanical interface for external CO₂ bottles and regulator panels

4.3.1.8 Thermal System

4.3.1.8.1 The MTF shall have two I-beams fixed on the roof to provide structural support and mounting points for a free cooler and a patch antenna mounting pole as shown in Figure 4-15.

4.3.1.8.2 The external free cooler shall be connected to the MTF thermal control system via the fluid lines as shown in Figure 4-15.

Figure 4-15: External free cooler fluid line connection to MTF TCS

4.3.1.9 Command and Data Handling

4.3.1.9.1 The MTF shall have a mounting pole installed on the roof, to allow mounting of a patch antenna for (backup) communication with the NM-III station, as shown in Figure 4-16.

Figure 4-16: WLAN Patch Antenna mounted on the MTF. (Left) CAD drawing of the patch antenna position (Right) Mounting interface for the patch antenna

4.3.1.10 Cable Channel

Note: It is necessary to provide adequate protection of cables from the harsh Antarctic environment. End of note.

4.3.1.10.1 The MTF shall have a cable channel around its exterior hull mounted to the top of each wall, as indicated in blue in Figure 4-17, which depicts the South side of the MTF.

Figure 4-17: South side of the MTF. (Blue) Cable channel

4.3.1.11 External Illumination

Note: The MTF shall have external lighting to provide general walkway illumination and specific illumination for the entry/exit door and emergency door. End of note.

4.3.1.11.1 *The external illumination shall be mounted on brackets which are connected to the MTF outer hull via three screws, as seen in Figure 4-18 for the South side of the Service Section container*

Note: Additional lights are located on the West side of the Service Section container, the North side of the Service Section container, the North side of the FEG container and the East side of the FEG container. End of note.

Figure 4-18: External lighting interface

4.3.2 Electrical Power Interface Requirements

4.3.2.1 Main power box

4.3.2.1.1 Main power connectors and pin assignments

The main power from the NM-III shall be connected to the MTF main power box using the connector type and pin assignments as shown in Figure 4-19.

Figure 4-19: Main power box connector type and pin assignments

4.3.2.1.2 Fusing concept and trip protection characteristics

The fusing concept of the MTF main power box shall be as shown in Figure 4-20.

Figure 4-20: MTF main power box fusing concept

The MTF main power box trip characteristics shall be as shown in Table 4-3.

Characteristic	Value
Control Voltage	24 VDC
Rated Current / max Fuse	80 A
Design Isolation Voltage	1.0 kV

Table 4-3: MTF main power box trip characteristics

4.3.2.2 Emergency Power Supply Characteristics

In case of NM-III main power interruption the Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) shall switch automatically from line power to battery mode (i.e. to power the specific devices connected to it) within ca. 10 ms. The physical characteristics of the UPS shall be as shown in Table 4-4:

Figure 4-21: Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS)

Note: The UPS shall consist of one control unit (APC Smart-UPS X 1500 VA, Rack/Tower LCD, 230 V) and three battery packs (External Battery-Extension for Smart-UPS X Series, Rack/Tower). End of note.

Characteristic	Value
Output power capacity	1.2 kW / 1.5 kVA
Nominal output voltage	230 V
Output voltage distortion	<5%
Output frequency	50/60 Hz +/- 3 Hz
Battery capacity	2592 mAh (864 mAh per battery extension)

Table 4-4: Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) electrical characteristics

4.3.2.3 Electrical power interface requirements for externally mounted components

4.3.2.3.1 Free cooler

4.3.2.3.1.1 Free cooler electrical power requirements

The MTF free cooler shall be provided with electrical power from the MTF main power box with characteristics as shown in Table 4-5.

Characteristic	Value
Voltage	3~ 400 V
Current	3.0 A
Power	1.52 kW

Table 4-5: External free cooler power supply requirements

4.3.2.3.1.2 Connector and pin assignment

The MTF free cooler power supply cable shall be connected to the MTF power supply box via the connector type and pin assignment as shown in Figure 4-22.

Note. For a detailed description of connector and pin assignments for the MTF free cooler power supply see document "Data sheet GMM phasecut compact 100/x.1" [RD14]. End of note.

Figure 4-22: Thermal control system free cooler – power connectors and pin assignment to MTF Power Box

4.3.2.3.2 MTF external lighting

4.3.2.3.2.1 MTF external lighting power interface requirements

The MTF external lighting shall be provided with electrical power from the MTF main power box with characteristics as shown in Table 4-6.

Characteristic	Value
Voltage	230 V
Power	34 W

Table 4-6: External lighting power supply requirements

4.3.2.3.2.2 Connector type and pin assignment

The external lighting power supply cable(s) shall be connected to the MTF power supply box via an M18 x 1.5 cable, with IP68 shielding.

4.3.2.3.3 Patch antenna

Note: The patch antenna name and model shall be: Ubiquiti PowerBridge M5. End of note.

4.3.2.3.3.1 Patch antenna electrical power requirements

The patch antenna shall be provided with electrical power from the MTF main power box with characteristics as shown in Table 4-7.

Characteristic	Value
Voltage	24 V
Current	1 A
Power	8 W

Table 4-7: Patch antenna power supply requirements

4.3.2.3.3.2 Connector and pin assignment

The patch antenna shall be provided by power over an Ethernet cable (pairs 4,5+; 7,8 return).

4.3.2.3.4 External cameras

4.3.2.3.4.1 External camera electrical power requirements

The MTF external camera shall be provided with electrical power from the MTF main power box with characteristics as shown in Table 4-8.

Characteristic	Value
Voltage	12 VDC/24 VAC
Power	9 W

Table 4-8: External camera power supply requirements

4.3.2.3.4.2 Connector and pin assignment

The external camera power shall be provided by power over an Ethernet cable (PoE IEEE 802.3af).

4.3.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

4.3.3.1 MTF Container Walls, floor and roof

4.3.3.1.1 The MTF container walls, floor and roof shall be insulated to limit the k-value to $<0.35 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$.

4.3.3.1.2 The MTF Service Section window shall be multi-layered to limit the k-value to $<2.5 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$.

4.3.3.2 External MTF cooling fluid lines/ free cooler

4.3.3.2.1 The external free cooler shall have the physical characteristics and performance capability as detailed in Table 4-9.

Characteristic	Value
Max. heat load	12.0 kW
Min. operating temperature	-40°C
Dimensions	2.65 x 1.145 x 0.95 m
Max. Power	1.52 kW
Mass	203 kg (empty)

Table 4-9: External free cooler physical characteristics and heat rejection capability

4.3.3.2.2 Free cooler pump characteristics

Note: The free cooler pump shall be the pump located between the free cooler and the thermal system hydraulic separator. It is located within the thermal system rack inside the Service Section container. End of note.

The free cooler pump shall have the physical characteristics and performance capability as detailed in Table 4-10.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Wilo/Stratos 30/1-10
Nominal Volume flow	1.68 m ³ /h
Nominal Pressure head	~60.8 kPa (6,2 mWs)
Dimensions	203 x 238 x 180 mm
Max. Power	190 W
Mass	4.2 kg

Table 4-10: External fluid cooling line pump characteristics

4.3.3.3 Internal MTF cooling fluid lines

4.3.3.3.1 Heat exchanger 1 pump characteristics

Note: Heat exchanger 1 shall be the plate heat exchanger transferring heat between the internal AMS thermal loop and the external cooling loop. End of note.

The heat exchanger 1 pump shall have the physical characteristics and performance capability as detailed in Table 4-11.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Wilo/Stratos 25/1-8
Nominal Volume flow	0.91 m ³ /h
Nominal Pressure head	~24.5 kPa (2,5 mWs)
Dimensions	203 x 238 x 180 mm
Max. Power	130 W
Mass	4.1 kg

Table 4-11: Heat exchanger 1 pump characteristics

4.3.3.3.1.1 Heat exchanger 2 pump characteristics

Note: Heat exchanger 2 shall be the plate heat exchanger transferring heat between the internal ISPR and LED thermal loop and the external cooling loop. End of note.

The heat exchanger 2 pump shall have the physical characteristics and performance capability as detailed in Table 4-12.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Wilo/Stratos 25/1-8
Nominal Volume flow	0.76 m ³ /h
Nominal Pressure head	~19.6 kPa (2,0 mWs)
Dimensions	203 x 238 x 180 mm
Max. Power	130 W
Mass	4.1 kg

Table 4-12: Heat exchanger 2 pump characteristics

4.3.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

4.3.4.1 External air inlet

Note: External air shall be brought into the Service Section via the external inlet mentioned previously, in order to cool the internal atmosphere. Further details on this fresh air supply system are presented in section 5.2.4. End of note.

4.3.4.2 CO₂ inlet

4.3.4.2.1 *The externally-mounted CO₂ bottles shall be regulated to allow injection of CO₂ into the FEG atmosphere management system at a rate of ~0.24 L/s.*

4.3.4.2.2 *Two CO₂ bottles shall be connected to the gas regulator panels simultaneously, to allow automatic switching from one bottle to another when one bottle is empty.*

4.3.5 Command & Data Handling Interface

4.3.5.1 CD&H characteristics

4.3.5.1.1 CD&H bandwidth

The data transmission capability from the MTF internal CD&H computers via the WLAN external antenna, NM-III, satellite, AWI ground station and land-line to DLR and end-users shall support a performance bandwidth as defined in Table 4-13.

Data link	Bandwidth / Data rate
MTF to NM-III	>1 Mbps
NM-III to AWI Bremerhaven	100 – 150 kbps
AWI to DLR Bremen	20 Mbps
DLR Bremen to UHBs	>4 Mbps

Table 4-13: CD&H performance bandwidth

4.3.5.2 Fiber optics cable

4.3.5.2.1 Connector type

The fiber optics cable from the Neumayer Station III shall be connected to the MTF internal CD&H computers via quadruplex LC 2,8-3 mm connector as shown in Figure 4-23.

Figure 4-23: CD&H connector type

4.3.5.3 Patch antenna

4.3.5.3.1 Connector type and pin assignment

The CD&H cable from the WLAN patch antenna shall be connected to the MTF internal Ethernet switch via 1 X 10/100 BASE-TX (Cat. 5, RJ-45) Ethernet Interface.

RJ-45 Connector Pin	Signal
1	TX+
2	TX-
3	RX+
6	RX-

Table 4-14: Patch antenna connector pin assignment

Figure 4-24: CD&H patch antenna connector type and pin assignment

4.3.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

None.

Note. Water, nutrients and other items and consumables will be transferred between the station and the MTF manually by the crew, using a transport sled. End of note.

5 MTF internal hardware interface requirements

5.1 Cold Porch interfaces

5.1.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

5.1.1.1 Wall Mounting Interface

Plywood reinforcement plates shall be incorporated into the Service Section container, as shown in Figure 5-1, to provide additional structural support for specific wall-mounted components.

Figure 5-1: Service Section container wall reinforcements

5.1.1.2 Sub-floor structure

5.1.1.2.1 Sub-floor structure design

The Cold Porch sub-floor structure shall have structural profiles and floor panels as indicated in Figure 5-2.

Note: The green line in the figure indicates a separation wall between the Cold Porch and the Service Section area. The area to the right of this line is the Cold Porch area. End of note.

5.1.1.2.2 Sub-floor structure height

The sub-floor structure shall provide at least 25 cm of clearance to allow the fresh water tank and waste water tank to be installed below the floor panels and structural profiles.

Figure 5-2: Service Section sub-floor structure layout

5.1.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

Note: As the main power box is located in the Service Section area, the electrical interface requirements for equipment located in the Cold Porch are discussed in Section 5.2.2, which covers electrical interfaces between the Cold Porch and the Service Section. End of note.

5.1.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

5.1.3.1 Tank heater

A heating element shall be installed in the Cold Porch, in between the fresh water and waste water tanks in order to maintain their internal temperature above 4.4°C (SELCO Products OA-60 RS Thermostat).

5.1.3.2 Emergency heater

Note: As the wall-mounted emergency heater in the cold porch is used to control the temperature of the air, it is discussed in section 5.1.4. End of note.

5.1.3.3 Fresh air heating element

Note: As the duct-mounted heating element for the fresh air supply system is used to heat the air entering into the Service Section it is discussed in section 5.2.4. End of note.

5.1.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

5.1.4.1 Emergency heater

A wall-mounted heater shall be installed in the Cold Porch to maintain the internal temperature of the air above 5 °C.

5.1.4.2 Fresh air supply system

Note: As the fresh air supply system supplies air into the Service Section, it is discussed in Section 5.2.4, which covers interfaces between the Cold Porch and the Service Section. End of note.

5.1.5 Command and Data Handling Interface Requirements

Note: As the CDHS system is located in the Service Section area, the CDHS interface requirements for equipment located in the Cold Porch are discussed in Section 5.2.5, which covers interfaces between the Cold Porch and the Service Section. End of note.

5.1.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

Note: The interfaces between the fresh water and waste-water tanks and other subsystem components are described in section 5.2.6. End of note.

5.2 Cold Porch to Service Section interfaces

5.2.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

5.2.1.1 Cold Porch Separation Wall

5.2.1.1.1 *The separation wall between the Cold Porch and Service Section shall be constructed of 'Trespa' high pressure laminate plates, steel profiles and mineral fiber insulation material.*

5.2.1.1.2 *The separation wall between the Cold Porch and Service Section shall be 10 cm thick*

Note: The separation wall will consist of 1 cm thick 'Trespa' plates, 8 cm profiles and insulation, and then another 1 cm thick 'Trespa' plates. End of note.

5.2.1.1.3 *The Cold Porch separation wall shall have an access door into the Service Section made of steel (with mineral fiber insulation board) material.*

5.2.1.1.4 *The access door into the Service Section shall open outwards into the Cold Porch.*

5.2.1.1.5 *The access door into the Service Section shall have the following dimensions:*

- Width 100 cm
- Height 200 cm
- Thickness 6.5 cm

5.2.1.1.6 *The Cold Porch separation wall shall have interfaces for utility lines as shown in Figure 5-3.*

Figure 5-3: Cold Porch separation wall utility line interfaces

5.2.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

5.2.2.1 Cable harness

The cable harness for the Cold Porch elements requiring electrical power shall be mounted in the side wall cable channel as shown in Figure 5-4.

Note: A cut-out is included in the separation wall for cables to pass through into the Cold Porch from the Service Section as indicated in Figure 5-3. End of note.

Figure 5-4: Service Section and Cold Porch cable harness

5.2.2.2 Fresh and waste water tank components

5.2.2.2.1 Tank heating elements

Note: Two tank heating elements will be installed between the fresh water and waste water tanks. The larger heating element (SSHB-624-360-240-P) is expoxied to the side of the fresh water tank, while the smaller heating element (SSHB-612-180-240-P) is expoxied to the side of the wastewater tank. A second smaller heating element is planned, but not yet expoxied to the top of the fresh water tank. End of note.

5.2.2.2.1.1 The main power box shall provide power to the Cold Porch tank heating element with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-1. The wiring of the cold porch tank heating elements in addition to their thermal switch shall be as shown in Figure 5-5.

Characteristic	Heating element 1	Heating element 2
Name / Model	SSHB-612-180-240-P	SSHB-624-360-240-P
Voltage	240 V	240 V
Power	180 W	360 W

Table 5-1: Tank heating elements electrical characteristics

5.2.2.2.1.2 The main power box shall be connected to the Cold Porch tank heating elements via a 16 American Wire Gauge (AWG) wire with silicone rubber insulation.

Figure 5-5: Cold Porch tank heater wiring

5.2.2.2.2 Fresh water tank submersible pump and filter combination

Note: This pump shall be installed in the fresh water tank to ensure circulation of the water in the tank and shall not provide water to any other subsystems. End of note.

5.2.2.2.2.1 The main power box will provide power to the Cold Porch submersible tank pump (including filter) with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-2.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	EHEIM pickup 200
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	6 W

Table 5-2: Submersible tank pump and filter electrical characteristics

5.2.2.2.2.2 The main power box 240 VAC power shall be connected to the Cold Porch submersible tank pump-filter combination via a small control box containing three individual manually controlled SPST switches (one controlling the pump-filter) as in Figure 5-6.

Figure 5-6: Cold Porch tank heaters, fresh water pump/filter and UV lamp wiring

5.2.2.2.3 Fresh water tank UV disinfection system

A UV system will be installed within the Cold Porch fresh water tank to disinfect that water stored within.

5.2.2.2.3.1 The main power box will provide power to the Cold Porch UV disinfection lamp with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-3.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	UV-EL / 2x TRS VG 16 AC PP
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	40 W max

Table 5-3: Cold Porch UV disinfection system

5.2.2.2.3.2 The main power box 240 VAC power will be connected to the Cold Porch submersible tank pump-filter combination via a small control box containing three individual manually controlled SPST switches (one controlling the UV disinfection system) as illustrated in

5.2.2.2.4 Sensors

Note: The sensors for the fresh and waste water tanks receive their power over their interface with the Argus box. As such, these sensor interface requirements will be discussed in section 5.2.5. End of note.

5.2.2.3 Cold Porch emergency heater

Note: The emergency heater will be plugged into an electrical outlet socket in the Cold Porch, rather than having a direct connection to the main power box. End of note.

5.2.2.3.1 The main power box will provide power to the Cold Porch emergency heater with the following characteristics, as listed in *Table 5-4*.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Dimplex EF 6/20
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	2000 W
Fuse	2 A

Table 5-4: Emergency heater electrical characteristics

5.2.2.4 *Fresh air supply system*

5.2.2.4.1 *Valve actuator*

5.2.2.4.1.1 The main power box will provide power to the valve actuator in the Cold Porch with the following characteristics, as listed in *Table 5-5*.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Siemens GQD321-1A
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	10 VA / 4.5 W

Table 5-5: Valve actuator electrical characteristics

5.2.2.4.1.2 The main power box will be connected to the valve actuator in the Cold Porch via a cable with the following connections and pin assignment:

Figure 5-7: Valve actuator wiring diagram

5.2.2.4.2 *Duct heating element*

5.2.2.4.2.1 The main power box will provide power to the duct heating element in the Cold Porch with the following characteristics, as listed in *Table 5-6*.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Helios C/RR/3/G 1 1/2
Voltage	230/400 V 3~
Power	1700 W

Table 5-6: Duct heating element electrical characteristics

5.2.2.4.2.2 The main power box will be connected to the duct heating element in the Cold Porch via a small control box containing three individual manually controlled SPST switches (one controlling both tank heating elements).

5.2.2.4.3 Fan

5.2.2.4.3.1 The main power box will provide power to the fan in the Cold Porch with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-7.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Iso 160-2E
Voltage	230 VAC
Current	1.16 A
Power	260 W

Table 5-7: Fan electrical characteristics

5.2.2.4.3.2 The main power box will be connected to the fan in the Cold Porch via a cable with the following connections and pin assignment (Figure 5-8):

Figure 5-8: Cold porch fan power connection

5.2.2.4.4 Humidifier

5.2.2.4.4.1 The main power box will provide power to the humidifier in the Cold Porch with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-8.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Airwin UB-1 Sonder
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	105 W
Fuse	2.5 A

Table 5-8: Humidifier electrical characteristics

5.2.2.4.4.2 The main power box will be connected to the humidifier in the Cold Porch by connecting the power cable (L-N-PE) to the humidifier IEC device socket.

Figure 5-9: IEC device socket

5.2.2.4.4.3 The main power box will provide a 0 to 5 V signal for control of the humidifier via cables connected to pin 7 and 8 of the humidifier's 10-poles plug.

Note: Factory default control signal for pins 7 and 8 is a 0 to 10 VDC signal. Shifting this to a 0 to 5 V signal requires adjustment of the humidifier's internal 6-poles DIP switch. End of note.

Figure 5-10: Humidifier 10-poles plug

10-poles plug pin	Function
1 / 2	Safety chain
3 / 4	Hygostat 1 (50%)
5 / 6	Hygostat 2 (100%)
7	+ control signal
8	- control signal
9	L1 48 VAC
10	N 48 VAC

Table 5-9: Humidifier 10-poles plug pin assignment

5.2.2.5 General lighting

5.2.2.5.1 The main power box will provide power to the general lighting units in the Cold Porch with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-10..

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Pacific LED WT 460C/460X
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	49 W

Table 5-10: General lighting electrical characteristics

5.2.2.5.2 The main power box will be connected to the general lighting units in the Cold Porch via a standard NYM-J 3 x 1.5 mm² power cable using European wiring colour standards.

5.2.2.6 Safety system

5.2.2.6.1 HTK command module

5.2.2.6.1.1 The main power box will provide power to the HTK command module with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-11.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Scenty GWA 401
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	<55 W

Table 5-11: HTK command module electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.1.2 The main power box will be connected to the HTK command module via a cable that passes through a cable gland in the HTK command module enclosure box (Figure 5-11) and is connected to the relevant input power terminal blocks.

Figure 5-11: HTK command module enclosure box showing power and sensor terminal blocks

5.2.2.6.2 HTK sensors

5.2.2.6.2.1 The main power box will provide power to the CO₂ sensor with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-12.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GSI 400B / 400T
Voltage	24 VDC
Power	Not specified on data sheet nor could be provided by the supplier

Table 5-12: HTK CO₂ sensor electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.2.2 The main power box will provide power to the O₂ sensor with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-13.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GSZ 300
Voltage	24 VDC
Power	4 W

Table 5-13: HTK O₂ sensor electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.2.3 The main MTF power box (smoke detectors separate to the HTK system) will provide power to the hardwired smoke detectors with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-14.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	ABUS RM1000
Voltage	12 VDC
Power	0.368 W

Table 5-14: Smoke detector electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.3 HTK alarms

5.2.2.6.3.1 The main power box will provide power to the combination alarm horn and red LED alarm light (1 x installed in Service Section, 1 x installed in FEG) with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-15.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	WERMA Signaltechnik LED horn WM Cont. Ton 424 120 75
Voltage	24 VDC
Current (consumption)	<80 mA acoustic <45 mA optic

Table 5-15: Combination alarm horn and LED alarm light electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.3.2 The main power box will provide power to the combination red/yellow/blue LED alarm light (1 x installed in cold porch) with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-16.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	WERMA Signaltechnik KombiSIGN72 649.000.02
Voltage	24 VDC
Current (consumption)	<30 mA

Table 5-16: Combination red/yellow/blue LED alarm light electrical characteristics

5.2.2.6.3.3 The combination red/yellow/blue LED alarm light includes an integrated buzzer (installed on the end of the traffic light LED alarm light) with the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-17.

Characteristic	Value
----------------	-------

Name / Model	WERMA Signaltechnik (<85 dB) 645 800 75
Voltage	24 VDC
Current (consumption)	<35 mA

Table 5-17: Buzzer electrical characteristics

5.2.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

Note: There are no interfaces between the thermal system rack in the Service Section and the components in the Cold Porch.

5.2.4 Air Management System Interface Requirements

Note: There is no specific AMS system for the Cold Porch. An electrical heater controls the Cold Porch ambient temperature automatically via a temperature sensor.

5.2.4.1 Fresh air supply system

The Cold Porch shall house a fresh air supply system to route 'fresh' external air into the Service Section

5.2.4.1.1 *The fresh air supply system shall have a flow control valve and actuator to regulate the air inflow into the Service Section*

5.2.4.1.1.1 The flow control valve shall be compatible with Ø160 mm ducting.

5.2.4.1.1.2 The flow control valve actuator shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GQD321-1A
Max. Torque	6 Nm
Run time (90° turn)	30 s

Table 5-18: Air flow valve actuator characteristics

5.2.4.1.2 *The fresh air supply system shall have a heating element to regulate the temperature of the incoming air*

5.2.4.1.2.1 The heating element shall have the following characteristics:

Figure 5-12: Fresh air system duct heating element

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	C/RR/3/G 1 ½
Number of heating elements	3
Material of heating elements	Stainless steel, mat. No. 1.4828

Table 5-19: Duct heating element characteristics

5.2.4.1.3 The fresh air supply system shall have a filter unit to filter the incoming air

5.2.4.1.3.1 The filter unit shall have the following characteristics

Note: The filter unit consists of a casing, a pre-filter and a HEPA filter. End of note.

Characteristic	Pre-filter	HEPA filter
Name / Model	HS Beta Pak 85	HS-Mikro SF
Filter class	F7	H13
Size	287 x 287 x 48 mm	305 x 305 x 78 mm
Pressure drop	<110 Pa	<250 Pa

Table 5-20: Fresh air system filter characteristics

5.2.4.1.4 The fresh air supply system shall have a fan to ensure a flow rate of at least 150 m³/h.

5.2.4.1.4.1 The fan shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Iso 160-2E
Size	231 x 343 x 358 mm
Max. air capacity	730 m³/h
RPM	2600

Table 5-21: Fan characteristics

Figure 5-13: Fan performance diagram

5.2.4.1.5 The fresh air supply system shall have a humidifier to regulate the relative humidity of the incoming air.

5.2.4.1.5.1 The humidifier shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Airwin UB-1 Sonder
Size	337 x 253 x 205 mm
Max. humidification capacity	0.5 kg/h
Max. fan performance	49 m³/h

Table 5-22: Humidifier characteristics

5.2.5 CD&H Interface Requirements

5.2.5.1 Harness

The Cold Porch command and data handing system harness shall be routed to the Service Section as shown in Figure 5-4.

5.2.5.2 Sensors

5.2.5.2.1 Atmosphere management sensors

5.2.5.2.1.1 The Cold Porch shall house one sensor to measure the ambient temperature and relative humidity. The sensor shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	EE071 HCT01-00D /PT1000
Range RH	0 – 100 %
Accuracy RH	+/- 2% (0-90% RH) +/- 3% (90-100% RH)
Range Temperature	-40 to 80°C
Accuracy Temperature	0.2 – 0.6°C

Table 5-23: Temperature and relative humidity sensor characteristics

Figure 5-14: Sensor accuracy as a function of temperature

5.2.5.2.1.2 The Cold Porch temperature and RH sensor shall be connected to the Argus box via Modbus interface:

EE071:

- 1...+UB
- 2...B-RS485
- 3...A-RS485
- 4...GND

M12x1 flange

Figure 5-15: Temperature and relative humidity sensor connectors and pin assignment

5.2.5.2.2 Fresh and waste water tank sensors

5.2.5.2.2.1 The fresh and waste water tanks shall have level sensors to determine the fill level of the tanks. The sensors are based upon LS02-2 (or similar) float switches and the two wire sensors are wired directly to dry contact channels on an Argus sensor input module..

Note: The fresh water tank shall have two level sensors to define a high and low set point, whereas the waste water tank shall have one sensor to define the high set point. End of note.

5.2.5.2.2.2 The fresh and waste water tank level sensors shall be connected to the Argus box via the following connectors and pin assignment:

5.2.5.2.2.3 The fresh and waste water tanks shall have a thermistor temperature sensor to determine the temperature of the liquids. The thermistors shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	10K Precision Epoxy Thermistor – 3950 NTC
Range Temperature	-55 to 125°C
Resistance (at 25°C)	10K +/- 1%

Table 5-24: Fresh and waste water tank thermistor characteristics

5.2.5.2.2.4 The fresh and waste water tank thermistors shall be connected to the Argus box via the following connectors and pin assignment:

5.2.5.2.3 Safety system sensors

5.2.5.2.3.1 CO₂ sensors

The CO₂ sensors shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GSI 400B
Range	0-5000 ppm
Output signal	4-20 mA

Table 5-25: CO₂ sensor characteristics

5.2.5.2.3.2 O₂ sensor

The O₂ sensors shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GSZ 300 T
Range	0 – 25 Vol.%
Accuracy	<+/- 1% (of measuring range)
Output signal	4-20 mA

Table 5-26: O₂ sensor characteristics**5.2.5.2.3.3 Smoke detector**

The smoke detectors shall have the following states:

- Normally Open (NO) or Normally Closed (NC) connection,
- 1 A @ 30 V DC

5.2.5.3 Actuators**5.2.5.3.1 Atmosphere management actuators****5.2.5.3.1.1 Emergency heater**

Note: The emergency heater has an automatic control to ensure the heater turns on when the ambient temperature drops below a certain point. End of note.

5.2.5.3.1.2 Fresh air system

Note: The fresh air system valve actuator, duct heating element, fan and humidifier are all controlled by regulating the power supply. The relevant physical interfaces have previously been described in section 5.2.2. Further details on the control logic can be found in the Software Interface Document. End of note.

5.2.5.3.2 Fresh and waste water tank actuators**5.2.5.3.2.1 Heating elements**

Note: The heating elements for the fresh and waste water tanks are controlled by regulating the power supply. No control signals or harness are connected to these elements. Further details on the control logic can be found in the Software Interface Document. End of note.

5.2.5.3.3 Safety system actuators

Note: The safety system combination horn and alarm lights (1 x Service Section, 1 x FEG) and combination red/yellow/blue alarm light and buzzer are all controlled automatically by the HTK Scenty GWA 401 command module. End of note.

5.2.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements**5.2.6.1 Fresh water tank**

5.2.6.1.1 *The fresh water tank shall provide water to the users via a fresh water pump, with performance characteristics as indicated in Table 5-27: F.*

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Shurflo Aqua King II Standard 3.0
Nominal Volume flow	6.43 LPM
Nominal Pressure head	1.4 bar
Dimensions	207.5 x 125 x 105.2 mm

Max. Power	91.2 W
Mass	1.92 kg

Table 5-27: Fresh water pump characteristics

5.2.6.1.2 *The fresh water tank shall be mounted in the sub-floor of the Cold Porch and connected to fresh water pump via ¼" diameter (6.35 mm OD) black polypropylene tubing to the fresh water pump which is connected to the Service Section Nutrient Delivery System (NDS) by 1/2" ID clear braided tubing.*

5.2.6.1.3 *The fresh water tank shall be connected to the Service Section Air Management System (AMS) by ¼" diameter (6.35 mm OD) black polypropylene tubing.*

Note: This interface is for the return of condensate water to the fresh water tank, rather than the supply of fresh water to the AMS. End of note.

5.2.6.1.4 *The fresh water tank shall be connected to the Service Section humidifier by ¼" diameter (6.35 mm OD) black polypropylene tubing.*

5.2.6.1.5 *The fresh water tank shall be connected to the Service Section sink by ½" ID clear braided tubing via the fresh water pump.*

5.2.6.1.6 *The fresh water tank feeder pipes shall be made of PVC.*

5.2.6.2 Waste water tank

5.2.6.2.1 *The liquid waste tank shall be connected to the drain of the Service Section sink by 4 cm diameter grey polypropylene piping.*

5.2.6.2.2 *The liquid waste tank shall be connected to the drain of the SS humidifier by ¼" diameter (6.35 mm OD) black polypropylene tubing.*

5.2.6.2.3 *The liquid Waste Tank feeder pipe shall be made of PVC that is resistant to the corrosive effects of all chemicals contained in the liquid waste.*

5.3 Service Section interfaces

5.3.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

5.3.1.1 Wall Mounting Interface

The Service Section container shall have plywood reinforcement plates at the locations indicated in Figure 5-1 to accommodate mounting of the indicated components.

5.3.1.2 Sub-floor Structure Interface

The Service Section sub-floor structure shall have mounting interfaces at the locations indicated in Figure 5-2.

5.3.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

5.3.2.1 Command and Data Handling System

5.3.2.1.1 Argus box

5.3.2.1.1.1 The main power box shall provide power to the Argus box transformers and power supply units with the following electrical characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Argus control system
Voltage	240 VAC
Max. Current	15 A

Table 5-28: Argus control system electrical characteristics

5.3.2.1.1.2 The main power box shall be connected to the Argus box according to the connections and pin assignments indicated in Figure 5-16.

Figure 5-16: Main power box connected to ARGUS box: connections and pin assignments

5.3.2.1.2 Command and Data Handling servers

5.3.2.1.2.1 The main power box shall provide power to the server computers with the following electrical characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Fujitsu Primergy RX1330 M2 LFF
Voltage	240 VAC

Max. Current	2.0 A
Max. Power	152 W

Table 5-29: CDHS server computer electrical characteristics

5.3.2.1.3 Display screens

5.3.2.1.3.1 The main power box shall provide power to the display screens with the following electrical characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Acer V196WLbmd
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	13 W (operating), 450 mW (standby)

Table 5-30: CDHS display screen electrical characteristics

5.3.2.1.3.2 The main power box shall be connected to the server computers via the UPS. From the UPS one power cable runs to each of the server PCs.

5.3.2.2 Thermal System

5.3.2.2.1 Pumps

5.3.2.2.1.1 The main power box shall provide power to the thermal system pumps with the following electrical characteristics

Characteristic	Free Cooler Pump	Heat exchanger 1 pump	Heat exchanger 2 pump
Name / Model	Stratos 25/1-10 PN10	Stratos 25/1-6 PN10	Stratos 25/1-6 PN10
Voltage	230 V	230 V	230 V
Current	1.3 A	0.7 A	0.7 A
Max. Power	0.19 kW	0.08 kW	0.08 kW

Table 5-31: Thermal system pumps (external loop) electrical characteristics

Characteristic	AMS Pump	ISPR pump	LED pump
Name / Model	Stratos 25/1-10 PN10	Stratos 25/1-8 PN10	Stratos 25/1-8 PN10
Voltage	230 V	230 V	230 V
Current	1.3 A	1.1 A	1.1 A
Max. Power	0.19 kW	0.13 kW	0.13 kW

Table 5-32: Thermal system pumps (internal loops) electrical characteristics

5.3.2.2.1.2 The main power box shall be connected to the thermal system pumps via the wiring denoted in Figure 5-17. Where L, N, PE represent the connections to the 230 VAC mains (no connection via Argus). The ports denoted SSM remain unused.

Figure 5-17: Power box to thermal control system pump wiring

5.3.2.2.2 *Valve actuators*

5.3.2.2.2.1 The main power box shall provide power to the three-way valve actuators with the following electrical characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Samson Type 5824-10
Voltage	230 VAC
Max. Power	3 W (per valve actuator)

Table 5-33: Three-way valve actuators electrical characteristics

5.3.2.2.2 The main power box shall be connected to the three-way valve actuators via a small enclosure box situated within the rack (Figure 5-18). The enclosure/distribution box distributes the 240 VAC supply power to the four valve actuators. Each valve is subsequently wired with its own distinct signal cable to the Argus box. This signal cable carries the 0 to 20 mA control signal which dictates the opening/closing position of the valve. The specific terminal blocks within each valve actuator connected for supply power (N,L) and signal (11, 12) are illustrated in Figure 5-19.

Figure 5-18: Valve actuator supply power distribution box

Figure 5-19: Valve actuator terminal block wiring

5.3.2.2.3 Sensors

Note: The sensors in the thermal system rack receive power over their connections to the Argus control box. End of note.

5.3.2.3 Atmosphere Management System

5.3.2.3.1 Fans

The AMS fans shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Ebmpabst K3G 250-AT39-74
Voltage	230 VAC
Max. Current	3.3 A
Max. Power	750 W (each fan)

Table 5-34: AMS rack main fan electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.2 Duct heating elements

The AMS duct heating elements shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Infra Rodon Duct Heaters
Voltage	230 VAC
Max. Power	3000 W

Table 5-35: AMS rack duct heating elements electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.3 Duct UV-lamp

The AMS duct UV-lamp shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	UV-Duct-FL 2/60HP
Voltage	240 VAC (with internal conversion in unit)
Current	0.8 A
Power	120 W (60 W per bulb)

Table 5-36: AMS rack duct UV-lamp electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.4 O₂ sensor

The O₂ sensor installed in the AMS rack (on return flow from FEG) shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Roscid Technologies, O2Tracer, O2T-2 (0-25% O ₂)
Voltage	10-35 VDC
Power	0.8 W

Table 5-37: Condensate pump electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.5 Condensate pump

The condensate pump shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Aspen Mini Tank Pump
Voltage	230 VAC
Current	0.1 A
Power	16 W

Table 5-38: Condensate pump electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.6 Condensate in-line UV-lamp

The condensate in-line UV-lamp shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Aquisense PearlAqua 6D
Voltage	12 VDC
Power	8 W

Table 5-39: Condensate in-line UV-lamp electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.7 Condensate flow meter

The condensate flow meter shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	IMsystem FCHM-POM-HD 0,01 l/min
Voltage	5-24 VDC
Power	Not specified on data sheet

Table 5-40: Condensate flow meter electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.8 CO₂ injection valve

The CO₂ injection valve shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Nadi CO3 18 DOP
Voltage	24 VDC
Power	11 W

Table 5-41: CO₂ solenoid injection valve electrical characteristics

5.3.2.3.9 CO₂ flow meter

The CO₂ flow meter shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	SMC PFM750S-C8-A-W
Voltage	24 VDC
Current	80 mA
Power	1.92 W

Table 5-42: CO₂ flow meter electrical characteristics

Connector pin numbers	Wire color	Description
1	Brown	DC(+)
2	White	Out 2/ Analogue output / External input
3	Black	Out 1
4	Blue	DC(-)

Table 5-43: CO₂ flow meter pin assignments

5.3.2.4 Nutrient Delivery System

5.3.2.4.1 Main circulation pumps

The NDS main circulation pumps (one in each tank) shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Red Dragon 3 Mini

Voltage	230 VAC
Power	15-50 W (adjustable)

Table 5-44: Main circulation pumps characteristics

The circulation pump is wired to the power box via a small Red Dragon pump controller box (Figure 5-20) which allows for the manual adjustment (via touch buttons) of the pump output.

Figure 5-20: Red Dragon circulation pump and pump controller box

5.3.2.4.2 Dosing pumps

The NDS dosing pumps shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	AgrowTek Peristaltic Pump AD2 / AD4
Voltage	12 VDC (120 VAC wall outlet)
Current	1 A
Power	12 W (4 pump version)

Table 5-45: Dosing pumps characteristics

5.3.2.4.3 Fresh water supply solenoid valve

The NDS fresh water supply solenoid valve shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Asco 8262G7 Solenoid Valve
Voltage	24 VAC
Power	16 W (holding)

Table 5-46: Fresh water supply solenoid valve characteristics

5.3.2.4.4 Solenoid pinch valves

The NDS solenoid pinch valve shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Cole Parmer GY-98302-54
Voltage	24 VDC
Power	4 W

Table 5-47: Solenoid pinch valve characteristics

5.3.2.4.5 Ozone generator

The NDS ozone generator shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Spa Ozone Generator Aquatic 2
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	6 W

Table 5-48: Ozone generator characteristics

Figure 5-21: Ozone generator wiring connector

5.3.2.4.6 Air pump

The NDS air pump shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Micro Diaphragm Gas Pump NMP830 KNE
Voltage	230 VAC
Current	0.3 A
Power	25 W

Table 5-49: Air pump characteristics

5.3.2.4.7 Sensors

Note: All sensors are provided with power over their connection to the Argus control box, unless otherwise stated. End of note.

5.3.2.4.7.1 pH sensor

The pH sensor, Atlas Scientific ENV-40-pH, which terminates with a female BNC connector shall be wired to the IXIAN pH transmitter's male BNC connector as illustrated in Figure 5-22, a representative image displaying pH and EC transmitters. This cable is subsequently connected to the "pH" terminal blocks (Figure 5-23).

Figure 5-22: Illustrative example of pH and EC sensor wiring to their respective transmitters. EC probe BNC to EC transmitter BNC connection shown (other EC probe and two pH probes not connected)

The pH transmitter is then connected to the Argus box via two conductors from the "4-20 mA" and "N/C" output terminal blocks as shown in Figure 5-23. The transmitter is powered via 24 VDC (accepts 14 VDC to 36 VDC) via the "14-36 VDC" terminal blocks. The other terminal blocks on the pH transmitter remain unused.

Figure 5-23: pH transmitter wiring connections

5.3.2.4.7.2 EC sensor

The EC sensor, Atlas Scientific ENV-40-EC-K0.1, which terminates with a female BNC connector shall be wired to the IXIAN EC transmitter’s male BNC connector as illustrated in Figure 5-22, a representative image displaying pH and EC transmitters. This cable is subsequently connected to the “EC” terminal block (Figure 5-24). The EC transmitter is then connected to the Argus box via two conductors from the “4-20 mA” and “N/C” output terminal blocks. The transmitter is powered via 24 VDC (accepts 14 VDC to 36 VDC) via the “14-36 VDC” terminal blocks. The other terminal blocks on the EC transmitter remain unused.

Figure 5-24: EC transmitter wiring connections

5.3.2.4.7.3 Temperature sensor (thermistor)

The thermistors employed in the NDS are of the adafruit, 10K precision epoxy 3950 NTC type. The thermistors are wired directly to the Argus System.

5.3.2.4.7.4 NDS tank level sensor

The continuous tank level sensors, Innovative Concepts CLM-2000-SS, installed in the NDS reservoirs (one per reservoir) within the NDS rack are 3-wire potentiometers with red wired to power, green to signal and black to ground. The sensors are wired to 24 VDC.

5.3.2.4.7.5 Ozone sensor

The ozone sensor is a standalone, self-powered (battery) sensing unit (not connected to Argus).

5.3.2.4.7.6 Leak sensor

The leak sensor, GRI 2800, shall be wired as illustrated in Figure 5-25. The sensors accept between 5 and 24 VDC.

Figure 5-25: Leak sensor wiring connections**5.3.2.5 Miscellaneous Equipment****5.3.2.5.1 Sink fresh water heater**

The fresh water heater situated under the Service Section sink is a Stiebel Eltron, SHU 10 SLi-2000W heater. This 10 L capacity, 2000 W heater has the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Stiebel Eltron / SHU 10 SLi-2000W
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	2000 W (0.31 kWh / 24 standby power)

Table 5-50: Sink fresh water heater characteristics**Figure 5-26: Sink fresh water heater****5.3.2.5.2 Observation cameras**

The internal Service Section observation cameras are powered directly via their Ethernet cable connection to the Service Section Ethernet hub via Power over Ethernet (PoE).

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Hikvision / DS-2CD2522FWD-I (2.0MP)
Voltage	12 VDC (PoE)
Max Power	5 W

Table 5-51: Service Section camera characteristics**5.3.2.5.3 Emergency heater**

The service section employs the same emergency heater as the cold porch. This heater has the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Dimplex EF 6/20
Voltage	230 VAC

Power	2000 W
Fusee	2 A

Table 5-52: Service Section emergency heater electrical characteristics

The emergency heater will be plugged into an electrical outlet socket in the Service Section, rather than having a direct connection to the main power box.

5.3.2.5.4 Server computer circulation fan

The server computer circulation fan is powered directly from the one of the server USB ports (5 VDC).

5.3.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

5.3.3.1 External free cooler

Note: The interface between the thermal system rack and the external free cooler has been described in section 4.3. End of note.

5.3.3.2 Atmosphere Management System

Note: The thermal system rack shall be connected to the dehumidifier in the AMS rack in the Service Section. End of note.

5.3.3.2.1 AMS Pump

Note: The AMS pump is the pump located between the AMS dehumidifier and plate heat exchanger 1. End of note.

5.3.3.2.1.1 The thermal system loop for the AMS dehumidifier shall have a pump with the following operational characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Wilo/Stratos 25/1-10
Nominal Volume flow	0.69 m ³ /h
Nominal Pressure head	~105.9 kPa
Dimensions	203 x 238 x 180 mm
Max. Power	190 W
Mass	4.2 kg

Table 5-53: External fluid cooling line pump characteristics

5.3.3.2.2 Three-way valve

5.3.3.2.2.1 The thermal system loop for the AMS dehumidifier shall have a three-way valve with the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Samson Type 3226
Nominal Volume flow	0.7 kg/h
KVS	4.0 m ³ /h
Pressure drop	8 kPa
Kv set point	4.7

Table 5-54: Three-way valve characteristics

5.3.3.2.3 Three-way valve actuator

5.3.3.2.3.1 The thermal system loop for the AMS dehumidifier shall have a three-way valve actuator with the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Samson Type 5824-10
Rated travel	6 mm
Standard stroking speed	0.2 mm/s
Standard transit time	31 s
Thrust	700 N
Dimensions	103 x 113 x 146 mm
Mass	0.75 kg

Table 5-55: Three-way valve actuator characteristics

5.3.3.2.4 Piping

5.3.3.2.4.1 The thermal system rack shall be connected to the AMS dehumidifier via DN20 copper piping.

5.3.3.2.4.2 The piping connecting the thermal system rack and the AMS dehumidifier shall be insulated with Flex HT Conel insulation material.

5.3.3.3 LED panels

Note: The interfaces between the thermal system rack and the LED panels shall be covered in section 5.4. End of note.

5.3.3.4 ISPR

Note: The interfaces between the ISPR and the thermal system rack shall be defined in section 6. End of note.

5.3.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

Note: The AMS interface requirements for the FEG AMS are presented in section 5.4 and section 5.5. The AMS interface requirements for the fresh air supply to the Service Section have been presented in section 5.2. End of note.

5.3.5 Command and Data Handling Interface Requirements

5.3.5.1 Sensors

Note: The EDEN system CD&H sensor interfaces to the ARGUS and LABVIEW applications are defined in the EDEN System Software Interface Document [RD13]. End of note.

5.3.5.2 Actuators

Note: The actuator system control via the ARGUS and LABVIEW applications are defined in the EDEN System Software Interface Document [RD13]. End of note.

5.3.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

Note: See section 5.2.6 for the interface requirements between the fresh water and waste water tanks and the Service Section components. End of note.

5.4 Service Section to FEG

5.4.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

5.4.1.1 Partition Wall

5.4.1.1.1 The Service Section and FEG high-cube containers shall be internally separated by an interior partition wall as shown in Figure 5-27.

Figure 5-27: Partition wall with door between Service Section and FEG

5.4.1.1.2 The partition wall between SS and FEG shall be made of 'Trespa' high pressure laminate plates, steel profiles and rockwool insulation material with a thickness of 10 cm.

Note: The wall consists of 1 cm 'Trespa' plates, 8 cm steel profiles and insulation, and another 1 cm of 'Trespa' plates. End of note.

5.4.1.1.3 The partition wall between the Service Section and the FEG shall contain a door for personnel to move between the sections as in Figure 5-27.

5.4.1.1.4 *The partition wall access opening between the Service Section and the FEG shall have the following dimensions:*

- Height 200 cm
- Width 100 cm
- Thickness ca. 10.5 cm (1 cm Trespa, 8 cm profile, 1 cm Trespa)

5.4.1.1.5 *The partition wall access door shall have a screen that can be pulled down to block light in the FEG from entering into the Service Section.*

5.4.1.1.6 *The partition wall access door shall open outwards into the Service Section.*

5.4.1.1.7 *The partition wall shall have interfaces for utility lines and air ducts as indicated in Figure 5-27.*

Note: To reduce the air exchange between the SS and the FEG, the cut-outs for the fluid utility lines shall be plugged with silicone (rubber) seals, as shown in Figure 5-28. End of note.

Figure 5-28: Utility line cut-out seals

5.4.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

5.4.2.1 Cable harness

5.4.2.1.1 *The electrical harness between the Service Section Power Box and the FEG Internal equipment shall be as shown in Figure 5-29.*

Note: A cut-out is incorporated into the separation wall between the Service Section and the FEG to allow cables to pass from one area into the other. End of note.

Figure 5-29: FEG cable harness

5.4.2.2 Command and Data Handling System

5.4.2.2.1 Observation Cameras and Plant Health Monitoring Cameras

The internal observation and plant health monitoring cameras are powered directly via their Ethernet cable connection to the FEG Ethernet hub via Power over Ethernet (PoE).

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Hikvision / DS-2CD2522FWD-I (2.0MP)
Voltage	48 VDC (PoE, IEEE 802.3af)
Max Power	5 W

Table 5-56: Observation and plant health monitoring cameras characteristics

5.4.2.2.2 Multi-wavelength imager

The multi-wavelength imagers are powered by 5 VDC via a Mini-USB connection. The imagers are provided power via Ethernet connection to one of the two FEG Ethernet switches and a Power over Ethernet to USB adapter installed between the Ethernet switch and imager. This power connection ensures that the imager's rechargeable (1160 mAh, 3.8 VDC, 4.4 Wh) lithium-ion battery maintains its charge. Data is transmitted via a wireless connection via the multi-wavelength imager's (modified GoPro) Blink adapter.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	GoPro Hero4
Voltage	5 VDC (USB)
Max Power	Not specified on data sheet

Table 5-57: Multi-wavelength imager characteristics

5.4.2.2.3 Wireless access point

The wireless access point is provided power via a Power over Ethernet connection to one of the two the FEG Ethernet switches.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Intellinet / 525251
Voltage	48 VDC (PoE)
Max Power	4 W

Table 5-58: Wireless access point characteristics

5.4.2.2.4 Ethernet switches

The Ethernet switches shall have the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	HP 2530-48G-PoE + Switch (J9775A)
Voltage	230 VAC
Current	5.8/2.9 A
Max. Power	476 W (382 W PoE)
Dimensions	44.3 x 25.4 x 4.45 cm
Mass	4.72 kg

Table 5-59: Ethernet switch characteristics

5.4.2.3 Thermal system

There are no electrically powered pieces of equipment associated with the thermal system located within the FEG.

5.4.2.4 Atmosphere Management System

5.4.2.4.1 Circulation fans

The eight ceiling mounted FEG circulation fans are connected via a small controller box to 230 VAC power. The small control box contains a manually controlled potentiometer to provide control to the circulation fan output. The control box also contains a manual SPST on/off switch for fan power. Each circulation fan has the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	EBM-Papst / QLN65/3030-3045
Voltage	230 VAC
Max Power	72 W

Table 5-60: FEG circulation fan electrical characteristics

5.4.2.4.2 Sub-floor space heater

The FEG sub-floor space heater is plugged into an open 230 VAC wall plug near the FEG exit door. The heater is run from a standalone wall-plug in thermal switch (Renkforce, UT300) and which activates the heater when the temperature drops below a user set value. The FUG sub-floor space heater electrical characteristics are as follows:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	TERM 2000
Voltage	230 VAC
Rated output	2000 W

Table 5-61: FEG sub-floor space heater electrical characteristics

5.4.2.5 Nutrient Delivery System

5.4.2.5.1 High pressure pumps

The high pressure pumps are provided power directly Service Section power and Argus boxes.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Flojet / R3811233
Voltage	230 VAC
Max Power	ca. 140 W

Table 5-62: FEG high pressure pumps electrical characteristics

5.4.2.5.2 Sump pumps

The FEG subfloor sump pumps are each powered by one 240 VAC to 12 VDC converter (CUI, VDRS-60-12) located in an enclosure box in the subfloor. The physical layout and installation of this hardware is illustrated in Figure 5-30. The voltage converters are powered directly from the Service Section power box. The FEG sump pump electrical characteristics are as follows:

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Whale / GW0950
Voltage	12 VDC

Max Power	Not specified on data sheet
-----------	-----------------------------

Table 5-63: FEG sump pump electrical characteristics

Figure 5-30: Left: FEG sump pumps (A, B) and the voltage converter enclosure box (C) containing the two 240 VAC to 12 VDC converters. Right: Voltage converters installed into the enclosure box.

5.4.2.5.3 Sensors

5.4.2.5.3.1 Sump pump level sensor

The sump pump level sensors (Whale BE9001) are integrated directly into the Whale sump pump boxes and shall be powered directly from the 12 VDC sump pump power line provided from the one of the two 240 VAC to 12 VDC converters in the FEG subfloor (CUI, VDRS-60-12). The power supply wiring from the 12 VDC output of the converters to the general sump pump boxes and corresponding sump pump level sensors is illustrated in Figure 5-31.

Figure 5-31: Sump pump level sensor wiring connections (3-way switch not implemented)

5.4.2.5.3.2 Pressure sensor

The system uses TE Connectivity MSP300, MSP3251P4-ND pressure sensors to measure the pressure in the lines following the high pressure aeroponic pumps. The pressure sensors are powered via the 24 VDC terminal blocks used to supply Modbus connected devices with power. The digital pressure reading is measured by the Argus Modbus cards.

Figure 5-32: Pressure sensor wiring connections

5.4.2.5.3.3 Leak sensor

The FEG leak sensors have the same electrical and general properties as that installed in the Service Section (see 5.3.2.4.7.6).

5.4.2.6 Plant Growth Chamber LED Illumination

5.4.2.6.1 LED panels

All types of Heliospectra LED panels (custom manufactured for the project) are supplied by 240 VAC. The high power panels incorporate a 240 W integrated power supply (Mean Well, HLG-240H-48) while the low power panels incorporate a 120 W integrated power supply (Mean Well, HLG-120H-48). The drivers provide 48 VDC to the LEDs. Each LED has its own power cable originating from the power box.

5.4.2.6.2 LED bars

The three Heliospectra commercial LED bars (L71G) are installed in the cucumber chamber in the FEG. Each LED bar is fed power from one PLED75W-072-C1050-D power supply from Thomas Research Products. Additionally a standalone timer (Legrand, 482812 T31) is installed in an enclosure box adjacent to the power supplies and allows the operator to manually set the on/off times of the LED bars. Additionally, each bar has its own respective SPST on/off switch. One power cable from the Service Section power box feeds all devices/hardware.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Heliospectra / L71G
Voltage	240 VAC (provided to LED bar power supply)
Max Power	75 W

Table 5-64: LED bars electrical characteristics

5.4.2.7 Safety system

For electrical and general information on the FEG safety related equipment, please reference the HTK CO2 sensor, HTK O2 sensor, HTK alarm and the wired and standalone smoke detector information provide for the Cold Porch and Service Section (same specifications).

5.4.2.8 Miscellaneous equipment

5.4.2.8.1 General Lighting

5.4.2.8.1.1 The Service Section Power Box shall provide 230 VAC power to the AC/DC converter of each of the FEG overhead lighting panels (x3) (Philips, Pacific LED WT 460C/460X). Each panel shall have a rating of 36 W.

5.4.2.8.1.2 The connector type (terminal blocks for L, N, G) of the FEG overhead lighting panels power converters shall be as shown in Figure 5-33.

Figure 5-33: FEG overhead lighting panel power connector

5.4.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

5.4.3.1 LED panels

5.4.3.1.1 The Plant Growth Chamber LED bars shall be cooled by water from the Service Section thermal control system. The input water temperature shall be between 16 and 20 °C.

5.4.3.1.2 The Service Section Thermal Control System shall remove up to a maximum of 4200 W of heat from the LED panels.

5.4.3.1.3 The Thermal Control System (TCS) in the Service Section shall provide water cooling via fluid lines to the LED panels of the FEG Plant Growth Chambers as shown in Figure 5-34.

Figure 5-34: TCS to FEG LED panel network cooling interface (FEG subfloor)

5.4.3.1.4 For each Plant Growth Unit rack one manual valve, see Figure 5-35, per level, shall control the cooling water flow rate from the Service Section Thermal Control System (TCS) to the LED panels.

Figure 5-35: Tacosetter Inline 100 flow control valve

5.4.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

5.4.4.1 Ducting

5.4.4.1.1 The Air Management System (AMS) in the Service Section shall provide airflow to the FEG Plant Cultivation Chambers via a duct system mounted in the MTF sub-floor as shown in Figure 5-36.

Figure 5-36: AMS air flow ducts between SS and FEG

5.4.4.1.2 The Air Management System (AMS) in the Service Section shall have a return air duct system from the FEG Plant Cultivation Chambers mounted at the MTF ceiling as shown in Figure 5-36

5.4.4.1.3 The Air Management System (AMS) shall provide a controllable airflow to the FEG Plant Cultivation Chambers via louvers in each chamber as shown in Figure 5-37.

Figure 5-37: Controllable air flow to plant growth chambers via louvers

5.4.4.2 Filter

5.4.5 Command and Data Handling Interface Requirements

Note. The FEG sensor types and signal characteristics are defined in the EDEN ISS Software Interface Control Document. End of note.

5.4.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

5.4.6.1 Nutrient Delivery System

5.4.6.1.1 Piping

5.4.6.1.1.1 The Nutrient Delivery System (NDS) in the SS shall provide bulk nutrients of adjustable composition to the Plant Cultivation Chambers in the FEG via a sub-floor pipe distribution system as shown in Figure 5-38.

Figure 5-38: Sub-floor piping configuration of the NDS in the FEG

5.4.6.1.2 Pumps

The aeroponic high pressure pumps (Flojet, R3811233) are connected to the NDS tanks via:

- 3/4" ID clear braided tubing (painted black)
- Plastic quick disconnect connectors (3/4" elbow to 3/4" NPT x 1/2" tubing)
- 1/2" black polypropylene tubing
- OBK stainless steel 3-way 1/2" female NPT ball valves
- Additional quick disconnect connectors and 1/2" black polypropylene tubing
- 1/2" tube adapter to 3/8" NPT male

When active, the pump feeds water to the plant growth trays via:

- Connection to the in-line pressure sensor
- 3/8" NPT to 1/4" tube adapter
- 1/4" diameter (6.35 OD) tubing
- To various 1/4" high-pressure fittings from AFT including pipe-Tee (AFT-01676), elbows (AFT-01675).

Figure 5-39: NDS pumps for feeding water to plant growth trays from NDS tanks

5.5 Future Exploration Greenhouse equipment interfaces

5.5.1 Mechanical and Structural Interface Requirements

5.5.1.1 Sub-floor structure

5.5.1.1.1 Mounting interface

The Future Exploration Greenhouse sub-floor structure shall have mounting interfaces at the locations indicated in Figure 5-40.

Figure 5-40: FEG sub-floor structure

5.5.1.1.2 Floor panels

The Future Exploration Greenhouse floor panels shall be 955 x 705 mm metal grates (although one of the end grates has a length of 730 mm) with 30 x 10 mm grid openings.

5.5.2 Electrical Interface Requirements

Note: The electrical interface requirements for the FEG components have been presented in section 5.4. No other electrical interfaces exist for the FEG. End of note.

5.5.3 Thermal Interface Requirements

Note: The Thermal interface requirements for the LED units have been presented in section 5.4. No other thermal interfaces exist for the FEG. End of note.

5.5.4 Atmosphere Management System Interface Requirements

5.5.4.1 Circulation fans

5.5.4.1.1 The FEG shall have 8 circulation fans installed near the ceiling, with one circulation fan per Plant Growth Rack.

5.5.4.1.2 The circulation fans shall have the following characteristics, as listed in Table 5-65.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Ebm-papst QLN65-3030-3045
Voltage	230 V
Current	0.56 A
Power	72 W
Air flow	410 m ³ /h
Pressure head	62 Pa
Dimensions	728 x 90 x 108 mm
Mass	2.80 kg

Table 5-65: Circulation fan characteristics

5.5.4.2 Humidifier

Note: A permanent humidifier is not foreseen for the FEG. A stand-alone unit may be temporarily installed during the start-up phase of the greenhouse.

5.5.4.2.1 During some operational phases, a stand-alone humidifier, with the characteristics listed in Table 5-66, may be positioned in the FEG to ensure sufficient humidification.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	Sanvia LB 50
Voltage	230 VAC
Power	170 W
Humidification capacity	1.9 L/h
Tank capacity	19 L
Dimensions	61 x 34 x 56 cm

Table 5-66: FEG humidifier characteristics

5.5.4.3 Sub-floor space heater

5.5.4.3.1 A space heater, with the characteristics listed in Table 5-67, shall be mounted underneath the sub-floor in the FEG.

Characteristic	Value
Name / Model	TERM 2000
Voltage	230 VAC
Rated output	2000 W
Dimensions	61.5 x 9.5 x 12.5 cm
Mass	2.5 kg

Table 5-67: FEG space heater characteristics

5.5.5 Command and Data Handling Interface Requirements

Note: The EDEN system CD&H sensor and actuator interfaces to the ARGUS and LABVIEW applications are defined in the EDEN System Software Interface Document [RD13]. End of note.

5.5.6 Water and Other Resource Interface Requirements

Note: The relevant interface requirements for the FEG components have been presented in section 5.4. No other interfaces exist for the FEG. End of note.

6 ISPR to Service Section Interfaces

6.1 Mechanical and Structural Interfaces

6.1.1 Integrated Rack Interfaces

6.1.1.1 Rack Dimensions

The integrated rack shall have the following dimensions:

- Width 1064 mm
- Height 1954 mm
- Depth 805 mm

6.1.1.2 Rack Mass

The integrated rack shall have a maximum total mass of 398 kg (excluding spares) see Table 6-1.

Note: The total mass value includes a margin of 20%. End of note.

Rack structure item	Mass (kg)
Primary Structure	121.0
Main Utilities Module	21.0
Upper Utilities Module	5.0
Power, C&DH Drawer	15.0
Nutrient Storage Drawer	23.0
Growth Chamber Drawer (Tall)	57.0
Growth Chamber Drawer (Short)	60.0
Illumination Drawer Left (Tall GC)	16.0
Illumination Drawer Right (Short GC)	16.0
TOTAL RACK (without margin)	332
TOTAL RACK (with margins)	398
Spares	146
TOTAL ISPR (with margins)	544

Table 6-1: Rack Mass Values (total and sub-elements)

6.1.1.3 Operations Protrusions

The integrated rack shall have the following protrusions to the rack front face as shown in Figure 6-1:

- handles
- drawer harness

These protrusions shall add maximum 100 mm to the rack depth of 800 mm.

Figure 6-1: Rack Front Side Operational Protrusions

6.1.1.4 Integrated Rack Front Side Layout

The integrated rack front side configuration shall be as shown in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2: Rack Front Side Layout

6.1.1.5 Rack Location

The integrated rack shall be located in the MTF Service Section as shown in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3: Rack Location in MTF Service Section

6.1.1.6 Rack Attachment Points to MTF

The integrated rack shall be attached to the MTF structure as shown in Figure 6-4 using the following mechanical fixtures:

- via 4x M8 screws through the bottom front aluminum profile to the MTF stainless steel pavement framework
- via 1x M8 screw through an L piece (mounted on the ISPR left wall horizontal aluminum profile) to the MTF structure.

Figure 6-4: Rack Attachment Points to MTF Structure

6.1.1.7 Rack Maintenance and Inspection Access

6.1.1.7.1 Rack Structure

Rack maintenance shall be performed only from the front side by removing the drawers if necessary as shown in Figure 6-5.

6.1.1.7.2 Drawer Access

Drawers shall be completely removable. A clearance of 730 mm (not including clearance for the operator) in front of the rack is necessary (see Figure 6-6).

6.1.1.7.3 Plant Cultivation Drawers

Plant cultivation drawers shall be accessible for maintenance and operations without complete removal by means of the inspection port on the left side (right side blocked by MTF wall for one of the chambers) (see Figure 6-7).

Figure 6-5: ISPR Rack Nominal Maintenance Access Clearance (example for one drawer, analogue for all drawers) - (all values in mm)

Figure 6-6: ISPR Drawer Removal Clearance (all values in mm)

Figure 6-7 ISPR Drawer Maintenance Access

6.1.1.8 Rack Utility Interface Panel (UIP) Connectors

The relative location of the integrated rack UIP connectors for power, data and cooling water shall be as shown in Figure 6-8.

Figure 6-8: Rack UIP Connectors Relative Location for power, data and cooling water

6.2 Electrical Power Interface

6.2.1 MTF Power Supply

The MTF shall provide the integrated rack with a single power interface rated at 230 VAC, 10A.

Note: The conversion of the 230 VAC to 24, 12 and 5 VDC shall be part of the internal design of the rack and shall be the responsibility of the rack developer. End of note.

6.2.2 Connector at UIP

The electrical power connector from the MTF to the rack UIP shall be a 230 VAC industrial 3 contacts 16A plug.

6.2.3 Rack Power Budget

6.2.3.1 Nominal Mode

The nominal power needs for day and night operational modes shall be 957 and 516 W respectively (see Table 6-2).

Note: Nominal mode is calculated assuming 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to tall crops and 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to short crops. End of note.

Note: nominal power needs include a 10% reserve margin. End of note.

	Power day - nominal mode (W)	Power night - nominal mode (W)
Primary Structure	0.0	0.0
Main Utilities Module	24.3	24.3
Upper Utilities Module	5.0	5.0
Power, C&DH Drawer	81.0	81.0
Nutrient Storage Drawer	40.4	40.4
Growth Chamber Drawer (Tall)	249.0	149.0
Growth Chamber Drawer (Short)	249.0	149.0
Illumination Drawer Left (Tall GC)	110.0	10.0
Illumination Drawer Right (Short GC)	110.0	10.0
TOTAL RACK (without 10% margin)	870	469
TOTAL RACK (with 10% margin)	957	516

Table 6-2: Rack Power Budget for Nominal Day and Night Modes

6.2.3.2 Peak Power

The peak power needs for the rack shall be 1325 W (see Table 6-3).

Note: peak power needs include a 10% reserve margin. End of note.

	Peak power (W)
Primary Structure	0.0
Main Utilities Module	24.3
Upper Utilities Module	5.0
Power, C&DH Drawer	81.0
Nutrient Storage Drawer	40.4
Growth Chamber Drawer (Tall)	415.0
Growth Chamber Drawer (Short)	415.0
Illumination Drawer Left (Tall GC)	110.0
Illumination Drawer Right (Short GC)	110.0
TOTAL RACK (without 10% margin)	1205
TOTAL RACK (with 10% margins)	1325

Table 6-3: Rack Peak Power Budget

6.3 Command and Data Handling Interface

6.3.1 Rack Command and Data Handling System

The rack including growth chambers shall be monitored and controlled from the MTF Service Section using the commercial based LabVIEW application hosted on a dedicated ISPR laptop.

Responsible: DLR, TAS-I

6.3.2 LAN Interface

The rack dedicated laptop hosting the LabVIEW command and data handling application shall communicate with the rack and growth chambers using a system LAN socket as specified in NI cDAQ™-9137 [RD8].

Responsible: DLR, TAS-I

6.3.3 Rack Sensors and Actuators

Note: The EDEN system CD&H sensor and actuator interfaces to the LABVIEW application are defined in the EDEN System Software Interface Document [RD13]. End of note

6.4 Thermal Control Interface

6.4.1 Cooling Water Interface with MTF

6.4.1.1 Cooling water flow rate

The cooling water inlet flow rate at the UIP interface shall be 190 kg/h.

6.4.1.2 Cooling water inlet temperature

The cooling water inlet flow temperature at the UIP interface shall be in the range 16 – 20°C.

6.4.1.3 Cooling water outlet temperature

The cooling water outlet flow temperature at the UIP interface shall be in worst case 25°C assuming maximum water inlet temperature, rack peak power mode and no thermal dissipation to environment.

6.4.1.4 Connectors

The MTF umbilical connectors for the cooling water inlet and outlet shall be attached to the UIP by self-locking ½" quick disconnects (QD) female of part type Swagelok SS-QC8-B1-810.

6.4.1.5 Connector location on rack UIP

The location of the water-cooling interfaces at the UIP is defined in Figure 6-9

Figure 6-9: Rack Cooling Water Inlet/Outlet Interface Position

6.5 Air Exchange Interface

Note: The rack volume shall be connected with the MTF Service Section in multiple positions. Thus the Service Section environmental parameters are required to model the gas exchange. End of note.

6.5.1 Rack Temperature and Relative Humidity

The gas exchange between the MTF Service Section and the internal rack volume shall provide for the following internal rack temperature and relative humidity (RH) range:

- Temperature and RH range (incl. different modes):
 - Day values are $T = 21^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 25\text{-}30\%$
 - Night values are $T = 18^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 25\text{-}30\%$

6.5.2 Carbon Dioxide Concentration

The gas exchange between the MTF Service Section and the internal rack volume shall provide for the following internal rack CO₂ concentration range:

- CO₂ concentration range
 - Nominal values ≥ 400 ppm (<750 ppm, FEG value)

6.5.3 Rack Gas Exchange Locations

The rack air volume shall be connected to the MTF Service Section volume at the following locations:

6.5.3.1 Growth Chambers air inlet

The Growth Chamber air inlets shall be located at the following locations (see Figure 6-10):

- Position: Growth chamber drawer front panel
- Topology: 20 mm x 50 mm 10 μ m stainless steel grid

6.5.3.2 Rack air outlet

The rack air outlets shall be located at the following locations (see Figure 6-10):

- Position: rack UIP (rack bottom-front side) as well as multiple locations (rack not sealed)
- Topology: multiple openings

Figure 6-10: Rack air exchange interface positions (light blue points). The air is ejected from the rack to the MTF through multiple openings (none-sealed environment)

7 General MTF Interfaces

7.1 Acoustic Interfaces

Note. Although EDEN ISS continuous and intermittent noise levels are not intended to fulfill space qualification criteria, the project shall aim to comply with the Noise Criterion (NC)-40 requirements as far as possible.

Irrespective of the NC-40 requirements the SS and FEG shall as a minimum comply with the EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG (NoiseVibArbSchVO- 6. March 2007 as specified in section 7.1.3. End of note.

7.1.1 NC-40 Continuous Noise Level Limits

The continuous acoustic emissions generated by each MTF audible noise source shall not exceed in any octave band center frequency between 63 Hz and 8000 Hz at a distance of 0.6 m the limits in Table 7-1.

Noise Limits Measured At 0.6 Meters Distance From The MTF Audible Noise Source	
Frequency Band Hz	MTF Audible Noise Source Sound Pressure Level (SPL) dB
63	64
125	56
250	50
500	45
1000	41
2000	39
4000	38
8000	37

Table 7-1: Continuous noise limits

7.1.2 NC-40 Intermittent Noise Level Limits

The intermittent acoustic emissions generated by each MTF audible noise source when measured at a distance of 0.6 meters shall not exceed the limits in Table 7-2.

Noise Limits Measured At 0.6 Meters Distance From The MTF Audible Noise Source	
Maximum MTF Audible Noise Duration Per 24 Hour Period	Total MTF Audible Noise Source A-weighted Overall (SPL) dBA
8 hours	49
7 hours	50
6 hours	51
5 hours	52
4 hours	54
3 hours	57
2 hours	60
1 hour	65
30 minutes	69
15 minutes	72
5 minutes	76
2 minutes	78
1 minute	79
Not allowed	80

Table 7-2: Intermittent noise limits

7.1.3 EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG Noise Level Limits

The MTF SS and FEG shall as a minimum comply with the EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG for noise levels in the work place as follows:

- Exposure limit values: $L_{EX, 8hr} = 87$ dB(A) and $P_{peak} = 137$ dB(Cpeak)
- Upper exposure action values: $L_{EX, 8hr} = 87$ dB(A) and $P_{peak} = 137$ dB(Cpeak)
- Lower exposure action values: $L_{EX, 8hr} = 85$ dB(A) and $P_{peak} = 135$ dB(Cpeak)

7.1.4 Noise Measurement Scenarios

The following MTF operational scenarios shall be executed to assure that the MTF complies with the EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG for noise limit in a work place environment as defined in 7.1.3

Service Section – Test Set:

Test Set 1 (SS 1)

AMS rack fans on nominal setpoint (70%)

Server computers running

NDS circulation pumps running (no dosing pumps)

Test Set 2 (SS 2)

AMS rack fans on nominal setpoint (70%)

Server computers running

NDS circulation pumps on and one dosing pump

Test Set 3 (SS 3)

AMS rack fans on at 100%

Server computers running

NDS circulation pumps on and one dosing pump

FEG – Test Set:**Test Set 1 (FEG 1)**

AMS rack fans on nominal setpoint (70%)

No NDS high pressure aeroponic pumps running

Test Set 2 (FEG 2)

AMS rack fans on nominal setpoint (70%)

One NDS high pressure aeroponic pump running

Test Set 3 (FEG 3)

AMS rack fans on at 100%

One NDS high pressure aeroponic pump running

Test Set 4 (FEG 4)

AMS rack fans on at 100%

No NDS high pressure aeroponic pump running

7.1.5 MTF As-Built Noise Levels

Note. This section provides a summary of the as-built MTF measured noise levels using the operational test scenarios in 7.1.4. End of note.

7.1.5.1 Compliance to NC-40 continuous noise limits

The MTF as-built noise levels in comparison with the NC-40 requirements are shown in Table 7-3. Some values violate the NC-40 requirements but see section 7.1.5.2.

Frequency (Hz)	Intensity	Nominal Ops	Worst Case	Nominal Ops	Worst Case	Notes
		SS Test Case 1 (dB)	SS Test Case 3 (dB)	FEG Test Case 1 (dB)	FEG Test Case 3 (dB)	
63	64	60.03	63.57	55.43	60.76	(1)
125	56	59,67	64.04	61.66	66.32	(2)
250	50	60.2	60.1	57.04	59.51	(3)
500	45	49.54	55	58.65	62.75	(4)
1000	41	41.13	44.68	49.86	56.88	(5)
2000	39	39.54	41.89	48.29	52.82	(6)
4000	38	32.93	35.71	43.29	48.45	(7)
8000	37	27.33	32.69	34.14	39.03	(8)

Table 7-3: MTF SS and FEG compliance with NC-40 continuous noise requirements

Notes:

- (1) All compliant
- (2) All over specification
- (3) All over specification (ca. 10 dB)
- (4) All over specification (SS: 5-10 dB, FEG: 13-18 dB)
- (5) All over specification (SS: 1-4 dB, FEG: 9-16 dB)
- (6) All over specification (SS: 1-3 dB, FEG: 9-13 dB)
- (7) SS compliant, FEG over specification
- (8) SS compliant, FEG partially over specification

7.1.5.2 Compliance to EU Noise Exposure Guideline

The MTF as-built noise levels in comparison with the EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG are shown in Table 7-4; all values are compliant with EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG and hence there is no need for personnel to wear hearing protection.

Test Set	MTF Test Scenario	Continuous Noise Level dB(A)	Peak Noise Level dB(Cpeak)	Test time	Noise Exposure L _{EX, 8h} dB(A)
SS 1	Service Section, Test set 1 (fans 70%, no dosing pumps)	58.4	87.6	6	57.2
SS 2	Service Section, Test set 2 (fans 70%, one dosing pump)	59.7	87.6	6	58.5
SS 3	Service Section, Test set 3 (fans 100%, one dosing pump)	63.8	91.9	6	62.6
FEG 1	FEG, Test set 1 (fans 70%, no aeroponic pump)	64.4	86.9	6	63.1
FEG 2	FEG, Test set 3 (fans 100%, one aeroponic pump)	69.6	89.5	6	68.3
FEG 3	FEG, Test set 2 (fans 70%, one aeroponic pump)	65.5	86.6	6	64.2
FEG 4	FEG, Test set 4 (fans 100%, no aeroponic pump)	69.2	89.8	6	68.0

Table 7-4: MTF SS and FEG compliance with noise requirements of EU-Guideline 2003/10/EG

7.2 Human Safety Interfaces

7.2.1 Fire Detection and Fire Handling

7.2.1.1 Primary smoke sensor system

The MTF shall have a primary smoke detection system comprising sensors mounted in each of the MTF cold porch, Service Section and FEG.

7.2.1.2 Smoke sensor system

The MTF smoke sensors shall be connected directly to the Argus system

7.2.1.3 Fire/smoke detectors

The MTF smoke detectors shall be of type ABUS RM1000 as shown in Figure 7-1.

Figure 7-1: Connected optical smoke detector

7.2.1.4 Acoustic and visual fire warning - MTF

In case of fire in the MTF a visual and acoustic warning shall be issued by the Argus system in MTF and a warning shall be visible (in addition to audio) on the MTF monitoring station in NM-III.

7.2.1.5 Central fire alarm horn

The horn of the central fire alarm shall be of type Siemens, FDS221-R.

7.2.1.6 *Smoke detector main signal link between MTF and NM-III*

The MTF primary smoke detector monitoring signals shall be linked to Argus and the fiber optics data link between MTF and NM-III.

7.2.1.7 *Smoke detector back-up signal link between MTF and NM-III*

In case of failed fiber link between MTF and NM-III, Argus shall automatically transmit the smoke sensor monitoring data to NM-III via the WLAN patch antenna.

7.2.1.8 *Secondary smoke sensor system*

A secondary smoke detector system shall comprise battery-powered optical sensors mounted in each of the MTF cold porch, Service Section and FEG.

7.2.1.9 *Secondary smoke sensor type*

The secondary smoke sensors shall be of type CAVIUS 2001-TK001 [RD12] with a 5-year lifetime.

7.2.1.10 *Secondary smoke sensor operation*

The secondary smoke sensors shall operate as stand-alone devices with no signal monitoring by Argus. In case of smoke detection, the sensor(s) shall issue an audible alarm.

7.2.1.11 *Fire Extinguishers*

The MTF shall have fire extinguishers (Class ABC) in the following positions (see Figure 7-2):

- 1x in the Cold Porch next to the main entrance door (2 kg CO₂)
- 1x in the Service Section next to the internal separation door to the Cold Porch (6 kg powder)
- 1x in the FEG next to the emergency exit door (2 kg CO₂)

Figure 7-2: Fire extinguisher and other safety relevant equipment positions in MTF

7.2.2 Ambient air CO₂ concentration Caution & Warning

7.2.2.1 CO₂ concentration detector system

The MTF shall use a LogiCO2 MK9 Detector Set 4 A system [RD10] that monitors Short Term Exposure Limit (STEL) and Time Weighted Average (TWA) levels of CO₂ and temperature at the sensor position.

7.2.2.2 CO₂ concentration detector components

The CO₂ detector system shall comprise the following components:

- A central unit with digital display
- Sensor units (up to 8x)
- 1x horn/strobe
- Separate electronic transformer for power

7.2.2.3 CO₂ concentration Caution & Warning alarms

The CO₂ concentration Caution & Warning shall provide the following:

- A green light shall be displayed in the central unit for normal safe conditions.
- An intermittent audible tone and a blinking red LED shall be issued if CO₂ concentration reaches 1.5% (pre-set low alarm) and the remote horn/strobe shall be activated.
- The Caution & Warning shall also be triggered if the TWA surpasses the 5000 ppm over an 8 hour period.

8 References

8.1 *Applicable Documents*

- [AD1] Antarctic Treaty. "The protocol on environmental protection of the Antarctic Treaty," Madrid, Spain, 1991.

8.2 *Reference Documents*

- [RD1] ESA, "Technology Readiness Levels Handbook for Space Applications", ESA, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, 2008.
- [RD2] International Standard Payload Rack to NASA/ESA/JAXA Modules Interface Control Document, SSP 41002, Revision P, 28 March, 2011.
- [RD3] Columbus Pressurized Payloads Interface Requirements Document, COL-RIBRE-SPE-0164, Issue 2, dated 01.11.2010.
- [RD4] EDEN ISS Plant Analysis Report, version 1.0, 2015.
- [RD5] Spacecraft Maximum Allowable Concentrations for Airborne Contaminants, JSC 20584, NASA JSC, November, 2008.
- [RD6] Decal Process Document and Catalog, JSC 27260F, NASA JSC, January 2010.
- [RD7] Air Chemistry Laboratory platform technical drawing (07311501).
- [RD8] National Instruments Device Specification for NI cDAQ™-9137 CompactDAQ "Eight Slot Controller with Quad Core Processor".
- [RD9] Siemens Sinteso™ S-LINE FDOOT241-9, FDOOT241-A, FDO241, FDT241 Automatische Brandmelder datasheet, <https://www.downloads.siemens.com/download-center/Download.aspx?pos=download&fct=getasset&id1=A6V10061738>
- [RD10] LogiCO2 MK9 DETECTOR SET 4 A datasheet, www.logico2.com/images/files/450_2049-datasheet.pdf
- [RD11] Loner Bridge System 900 data sheet, <https://www.blacklinesafety.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Loner-Bridge-Data-sheet-EN-2015-10.pdf>
- [RD12] CAVIUS 5 Year Smoke Alarm data sheet, <http://www.cavius.com/upl/website/manuals-product-sheets/5Ysmokeproductsheet2.pdf>
- [RD13] EDEN ISS System Software Interface Control Document, EDEN ISS-DLR-WP2.1-D2.3-Software Interface Document-v2.0
- [RD14] Data sheet GMM phasecut compact 100/x.1, ERP no.: 5205494 / 5205495, V_3.0, www.guentner.de

9 Appendix

Simplified/non-comprehensive EDEN ISS sensor and actuator wiring log.

NDS Pumps			
	+	-	
L1 - Pump 1	Red	Black	
L2 - Pump 2	Pink	Purple	
L3 - Pump 3	Yellow	Green	
L4 - Pump 4	Brown	Blue	
R1 - Pump 5	Red	Black	
R2 - Pump 6	Pink	Purple	
R3 - Pump 7	Yellow	Green	
R4 - Pump 8	Brown	Blue	
NDS Pump Pressure Sensors - FEG			
	24 VDC (terminal)	Signal (Modbus Channel 1-8)	
L1	Red	Black	
L2	White	Green	
L3	Red	Black	
L4	White	Green	
R1	Red	Black	
R2	White	Green	
R3	Red	Black	
R4	White	Green	
NDS pH and EC Sensors			
	Signal	Ground	
pH1 (Tank 1)	Red	-	
pH2 (Tank 1)	Brown	-	
pH1 (Tank 2)	Black	-	
pH2 (Tank 2)	Blue	-	
EC1 (Tank 1)	Pink	-	
EC2 (Tank 1)	Yellow	-	
EC1 (Tank 2)	Purple	-	
EC2 (Tank 2)	Green	-	
NDS Acid Base Solenoids			
	+	-	
Acid	Red	Black	
Base	White	Green	
NDS Acid Base Pumps			

	+	-	
Acid	Red	Black	
Base	White	Green	
NDS Dosing Pumps			
	+	-	
A	Red	Black	
B	White	Green	
C	Red	Black	
D	White	Green	
NDS Tank Level Sensor			
3 conductor wire - matched the red, green and black wires			
NDS On/Off Flow Switch			
+	-	Argus	
Black	White	CHA+	
Black	White	CHB+	
NDS FEG Floor Sump Pump Level Sensors			
	+	-	
Left side sump pump (#1)	Red	Black	
Right side sump pump (#2)	Green	White	
NDS Cold Porch - Sensor Wiring			
	+	-	
Waste level high	Purple	Pink	
Fresh water high	White	Grey	
Fresh water low	Green	Yellow	
Temperature CPO 1	Brown	Blue	
Temperature CPO 2	Red	Black	
NDS Rec Pumps in Tank Pumps (Royal Exclusiv)			
<i>Phoenix Contact Quickon</i>			
Pin 1	Brown		
Pin 2	Black		
Pin 3	Grey		
Pin 4	Green/Yellow GND		
NDS Rack Fresh Water Solenoids			
Valve	Cable (4 conductor cable)		
Red 1	Red		
Red 2	Black		
Green/Yellow	Green		
NDS Leak Sensor (FEG)			

Sensor Side	Wire	Argus	
Red	1	24 VDC (power board)	
Black	2	see pic	
NDS Leak Sensor (SES)			
Sensor Side	Wire	Argus	
Red	Red	24 VDC (power board)	
Black	Black	see pic	
CP-G OP1			
A: red-black	ILS left side		
B: pink-purple	ISPR		
C: yellow-green	ILS right side		
D: brown-blue	Thermal		
CP-G OP2			
A: red-black	AMS		
B: pink-purple	NDS-SS		
C: yellow-green	NDS-FEG		
AMS T/RH Modbus Sensors (EE071)			
Argus Sensor Name	Sensor Code	Location in MTF	
AMS-FEG TRH PHM1	AMS.TRH.PHM.1 Slave ID: 104	Left middle top (B1)	
AMS-FEG TRH PHM2	AMS.TRH.PHM.2 Slave ID: 105	Left middle bottom (B2)	
AMS-FEG TRH PHM3	AMS.TRH.PHM.3 Slave ID: 101	Left near emergency exit (B3)	
AMS-FEG TRH PHM4	AMS.TRH.PHM.4 Slave ID: 107	Right near Service Section (B4)	
AMS-FEG AMS 1	AMS.TRH.1 Slave ID: 106	In AMS rack by UV light	
AMS-FEG AMS 2	AMS.TRH.2 Slave ID: 102		
AMS-SES TRH SES	AMS.TRH.SES Slave ID: 103		
AMS-CP CP	AMS.TRH.CP Slave ID: 100		
AMS T/RH Modbus Sensors (EE071) Wiring (note: a different cable was used for some sensors - numbered cable)			
Sensor Side	Wire	Modbus	Other Cables
Black	Black	Comm	Green & Yellow
Brown	Red	24 VDC	1
Blue	Green	Data+	2
White	White	Data-	3
CP-A OP4			
	+	-	
NDS Rec Pump Tank 1	Red	Black	
NDS Rec Pump Tank 2	Pink	Purple	
NDS FW Pump	Yellow	Green	
Ozone	Brown	Blue	
AMS Rack Top Fan ("Fan 1")			

Fan	Wire (4 cond. using 2)	Argus	
Pin 6 (4-20 mA)	Red	Top-row: Source (+)	
Pin 8 (GND)	Green	Top-row: Sink (-)	
AMS Rack Bottom Fan ("Fan 2)			
Fan	Wire (2 cond. using 2)	Argus	
Pin 6 (4-20 mA)	Red	Top-row: Source (+)	
Pin 8 (GND)	Black	Top-row: Sink (-)	
AMS Heater Air Loop			
Pauls Box	Wire	Argus	
3	Red	Top-row: Source (+)	
4	Black	Top-row: Sink (-)	
AMS Heater Air In			
Pauls Box	Wire	Argus	
7	Pink	Top-row: Source (+)	
8	Purple	Top-row: Sink (-)	
AMS Air Flow Rate Modbus Wiring		AMS Air Flow Rate Sensor Side	
Wire	Modbus	AMS rack back	
Green and Yellow	Comm (terminal)	2	
1	24 VDC (terminal)	3	
2	Data+ (Modbus Channel 1)	1	
3	Data- (Modbus Comm)	yellow-green	
		AMS rack front	
AMS Temp Air In 1/2			
	+	-	
Temp Air In 1	White	Blue	
Temp Air In 2	Pink	Brown	
AMS PHM Omni Sensor 1 (TRH, PAR, CO2)			
Wire	Argus		
Red	Omni PWR		
Black	CHA+		
AMS PHM Omni Sensor 2 (TRH, PAR, CO2)			
Wire	Argus		
Red	Omni PWR		
Black	CHB+		
AMS O2 Modbus Wiring			
Wire	Modbus		
Red	24 VDC (terminal)		
Black	Signal (Modbus Channel 2)		

TCS Pressure Modbus Wiring			
Sensor Side	Wire	Modbus	
1	Brown	24 VDC (terminal)	
2 (n.c.)	White	-	
3	Blue	Signal (Modbus Channel 5-8)	
4 (n.c.)	Black	-	
TCS Cooling Valves			
Valve	Wire	Argus	Other Cable (Pwr)
Pin 11	Brown	Top-row: Source (+)	Red = Live
Pin 12	White	Top-row: Sink (-)	Black = Neutral
TCS Radiator Temp Cable			
Sensor Side	Wire	Argus	
White	Blue	-	
Pink	Brown	+	
TCS Temp Outside 1/2			
	+	-	
Temp Outside Window (#1)	White	Black	
Temp Outside Exit (#2)	White	Black	
TCS Freecooler Argus GND => AI3 in SPS			
SAF Smoke Detectors			
Sensor Side	Wire	Connection	
12-	Blue	Power box	
12+	Brown	Power box	
Alarm +	Black	Argus data	
Alarm -	White	Argus data	
PDS Temp Electro Box			
+	-		
Red	Black		